

CHILD
RESCUE

ChildRescue
“Collective Awareness Platform for Missing Children
Investigation and Rescue”

D1.1 – User Requirements

Workpackage: WP1 – ChildRescue Operational Requirements and Methodology
Definition

Authors:	NTUA, S5, UBITECH, SILO
Status:	Final
Date:	31/03/2018
Version:	1.0
Classification:	Public

Disclaimer:

The ChildRescue project is co-funded by the Horizon 2020 Programme of the European Union. This document reflects only authors' views. The EC is not liable for any use that may be done of the information contained therein

ChildRescue Project Profile

Grant Agreement No.: 780938

Acronym:	ChildRescue
Title:	Collective Awareness Platform for Missing Children Investigation and Rescue
URL:	http://www.childrescue.eu
Start Date:	01/01/2018
Duration:	36 months

Partners

	National Technical University of Athens (NTUA), Decision Support Systems Laboratory, DSSLab <u>Co-ordinator</u>	Greece
	European Federation for Missing and Sexually Exploited Children AISBL - Missing Children Europe (MCE)	Belgium
	The Smile of the Child (SoC)	Greece
	Foundation for Missing and Sexually Exploited Children – (Child Focus)	Belgium
	Hellenic Red Cross (RC)	Greece
	Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences (FRA-UAS)	Germany
	SingularLogic Romania Computer Applications SRL (SILO)	Greece
	Ubitech Limited (UBITECH)	Cyprus
	MADE Group (MADE)	Greece
	SUITE5 DATA INTELLIGENCE SOLUTIONS LTD (SUITE5)	Cyprus

Document History

Version	Date	Author (Partner)	Remarks
0.1	6/02/2018	Ariadni Michalitsi, Dimitris Varoutas (NTUA)	ToC
0.2	6/03/2018	Christos Ntanos, Dimitris Varoutas (NTUA)	The Missing Children Emergency Use Case, Discovery and Identification Use Case of Unaccompanied Minors, Approach for Requirements Elicitation
0.3	12/03/2018	Dimitris Varoutas, Ariadni Michalitsi (NTUA)	AS-IS scenario & Identified Challenges for the two Use Cases
0.31	15/03/2018	Nefeli Bountouni (SILO)	Added contributions by SILO (sections 3.1.3, 3.2.3)
0.32	16/03/2018	Minas Pertselakis (SUITE5)	Added contributions by SUITE5 (section 4.2)
0.33	16/03/2018	George Vafeiadis (UBITECH)	Added contributions by UBITECH (section 4.1)
0.4	23/03/2018	Christos Ntanos, Dimitris Varoutas, Ariadni Michalitsi (NTUA)	Updated TO-BE scenarios for the two Use Cases
0.41	27/03/2018	Nefeli Bountouni (SILO)	Updated contributions by SILO (sections 3.1.3, 3.2.3)
0.5	28/03/2018	Christos Ntanos, Dimitris Varoutas, Ariadni Michalitsi (NTUA)	Consolidation of Inputs & Internal Review, Ready-for-review version
0.6	28/03/2018	Nel Broothaerts (CF)	Review and Corrections
0.7	30/03/2018	Antonia Tsirigoti(SoC)	Review and Corrections
0.8	31/03/2018	Zefi Thanasoula (RC) Maria Liandri (RC)	Review and Corrections
0.9	31/3/2018	Dimitris Varoutas (NTUA)	Aggregation of reviewed versions
0.95	31/03/2018	Evmorfia Biliri	Quality Control
1.00	31/03/2018	Christos Ntanos (NTUA)	Final Version to be submitted

Executive Summary

This deliverable is part of ChildRescue WP1 – ChildRescue Operational Requirements and Methodology Definition and specifically, it represents the work conducted for T1.1 – Identification of Stakeholders’ Needs and User Requirements.

The aim of this deliverable, according to the DoA, is to provide the ChildRescue user needs and requirements as well as the framework on which all research and development activities of the project to follow will be based.

In that respect, being the first deliverable of the work package, it defines the ChildRescue Requirements from three different perspectives: the business requirements, the stakeholder requirements and the business requirements.

The business requirements section deals with the identification of all stakeholders of the missing children cases and introduces the approach for the requirements elicitation. Afterwards, stakeholders requirements are analysed into the two ChildRescue Use Cases, that of “Missing Children Emergency Use Case” (SoC and Child Focus (CF)) and that of “Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minors Use Case” (RC), where the AS-IS scenarios for each of these two use cases are identified, leveraging the valuable input gained from the interviews conducted with the pilot partners (SoC, CF and RC) and the TO-BE scenarios are introduced to reveal the ChildRescue value proposition. A first approach for the derived user requirements is also extracted for each use case. Finally, a first version of the general ChildRescue system requirements is delivered, distinguishing them into functional and non-functional ones, along with a 1st iteration of the ChildRescue user stories. In order to also provide to its readers a comprehensible view of the ChildRescue approach, its value proposition and the distinction among the different, recognised actors and their distinct, access levels, two scenarios are presented, delineating a missing children mission through ChildRescue for the two project’s use cases.

An update of the present deliverable is organised for the second year of the project and specifically M21 under D1.4 “ChildRescue Integrated Methodology, Release II”, which is a final deliverable for WP1, concentrating all the work conducted under this WP.

Table of Contents

1	Introduction	8
1.1	Purpose & Scope	8
1.2	Structure of the deliverable	8
1.3	Relation to other WPs & Tasks	9
2	Business Requirements	10
2.1	Stakeholders' Identification	10
2.2	ChildRescue Approach for Requirements Elicitation	14
3	Stakeholders Requirements	16
3.1	The Missing Children Emergency Use Case.....	16
3.1.1	AS-IS scenario & Identified Challenges	16
3.1.1.1	Preparation and Profiling	18
3.1.1.2	Coordination and Collaboration	20
3.1.1.3	Action Stage	21
3.1.1.4	Archiving	25
3.1.2	TO-BE scenario	25
3.1.2.1	Preparation and Profiling	25
3.1.2.2	Coordination and Collaboration	26
3.1.2.3	Action Stage	27
3.1.2.4	Archiving	27
3.1.3	Derived User Requirements	28
3.2	Discovery and Identification Use Case of Unaccompanied Minors.....	31
3.2.1	AS-IS scenario & Identified Challenges	31
3.2.1.1	Preparation and Profiling	36
3.2.1.2	Coordination and Collaboration	38
3.2.1.3	Action Stage	39
3.2.1.4	Archiving	40
3.2.2	TO-BE scenario	40
3.2.2.1	Preparation and Profiling	40
3.2.2.2	Coordination and Collaboration	41
3.2.2.3	Action Stage	42
3.2.2.4	Archiving	42
3.2.3	Derived User Requirements	43
4	System Requirements	45
4.1	Generalised System Requirements	45
4.1.1	Functional Requirements	46

4.1.2	Non-functional Requirements.....	48
4.2	1st iteration of User Stories.....	49
4.2.1	USE CASE SCENARIO 1: Missing Children Emergency	52
4.2.2	USE CASE SCENARIO 2: Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minor and natural disaster	54
5	Conclusions	56
	Annex I: References	58
	Annex II: Questionnaires.....	59
	Annex III: User Stories By Actor	64

List of Figures

Figure 1-1 Relation to other WPs/tasks.....	9
Figure 3-1 MCO Missing Child Process Part 1	17
Figure 3-2 MCO Missing Child Process Part 2	18
Figure 3-3 Accommodation of Unaccompanied Minors	34
Figure 3-4 The Tracing Service	35
Figure 4-1: Requirement Specification	45

List of Tables

Table 2-1 ChildRescue Stakeholders	10
Table 3-1 Derived User Requirements for the Missing Children Emergency Use Case.....	28
Table 3-2 Derived User Requirements for the Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minors Use Case	43
Table 4-1 General Functional Requirements.....	46
Table 4-2 Functional Requirements for the Missing Children Emergency Use Case.....	47
Table 4-3 Functional Requirements for the Discovery and Identification Use Case of Unaccompanied Minors.....	47
Table 4-4 Non-functional Requirements.....	48
Table 4-5 ChildRescue Platform’s Actors	51

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose & Scope

This deliverable reports the ChildRescue user needs, and the collected and analysed user requirements. ChildRescue is guided by the vision to reduce the primary time between the moment a child is reported missing and the one when it is found, by developing an integrated methodology that will transform the way missing children investigations are currently held. At the same time, it aims to enhance the coordination between hosting facilities and NGOs running hosting facilities for unaccompanied migrant minors to track the relocation of those minors between hosting facilities and countries, even if they present themselves without identification, or new identification papers when reaching another destination, aiming to predict, prevent, and act effectively to protect their best interests in case of a disappearance. In this respect, it places particular emphasis on the study of current AS-IS procedures and the exploration of TO-BE future improved scenarios, and the extraction thereby of the requirements that will make this transformation possible.

The present deliverable is released within the context of Work Package 1 “ChildRescue Operational Requirements and Methodology Definition” and is particularly associated with Task 1.1 “Identification of Stakeholders’ Needs and User Requirements”. Essentially focusing on the end user perspective, the latter pursues the identification of the challenges perceived and the user needs and requirements with regard to missing children investigation procedures and targets to guide and provide input for the research and development activities of the project. Along the above lines, the deliverable at hand reports on the identified user needs and the collected and analysed user requirements for the ChildRescue environment.

1.2 Structure of the deliverable

The rest of the document at hand is structured as follows:

- Section 2 exposes the ChildRescue solution business requirements. In this respect, it describes the stakeholder groups involved in missing children investigation, explains the reasons and motivation for transforming the relevant procedures and outlines the objectives to be attained, whereas it outlines the approach to be adopted for the elicitation of user requirements.
- Section 3 then reports on the identified stakeholder requirements both for the Missing Children Emergency use case (Section 3.1), as well as for Discovery and Identification use case of Unaccompanied Minors (Section 3.2). For each use case, the document analyses the AS-IS scenario and identified challenges and juxtaposes to these the improved TO-BE scenario, in order to derive the user requirements.
- Section 4 then transforms the latter, namely the user requirements, into system requirements, which along with the provision of the generalised system requirements, a 1st iteration of the user stories for the ChildRescue solution is also presented. Two use case scenarios are also shaped to demonstrate in a clearer manner, which are the roles of the various actors identified and how a concrete scenario for a missing child mission can be formed using ChildRescue.
- Section 5 summarises the contents of the deliverable and reports relevant conclusions, while a number of Annexes incorporate any references used for this deliverable, as well as the set of questionnaires that have been utilised during the requirements’ elicitation process.

1.3 Relation to other WPs & Tasks

The user requirements, elicited by Task 1.1 and reported in the present deliverable are going to provide input for both the ChildRescue platform architecture and specifications in work package 3 and T3.1 in specific, as well as for the elaboration of the validation framework in work package 4 (T4.1). The update of the user requirements will be a continuous process throughout the project's lifecycle and will be promoted in particular by the results of WP3 and especially "T3.4 - ChildRescue Platform Technical Verification" and WP4 through "T4.3 - ChildRescue Platform Deployment, Operation and Support" and "T4.6 - ChildRescue Pilots Evaluation, Lessons Learnt and Impact Assessment". The final version of the user requirements will be documented along with the integrated ChildRescue methodology in deliverable D1.4.

Figure 1-1 Relation to other WPs/tasks

2 Business Requirements

2.1 Stakeholders' Identification

One of the most important steps in the development of a solution is determining what the stakeholders actually expect from it. Thus, it is essential to identify all persons and institutions involved in or influenced by the development, construction and the use of such a solution and document their requirements. The purpose of this chapter is to identify all stakeholders, namely all persons and organisations who have a potential interest on the future system and therefore normally make demands on it.

Bringing together all stakeholders involved in the value chain of the missing children investigations, ChildRescue will deliver a viable and sustainable solution for missing children response organisations, volunteer organisations and NGOs in Europe, with the credentials to be customised and adopted at an international level, according to each country's underlying regulatory framework.

During the user requirements' development, the stakeholders and their relationship with ChildRescue is essential for the platform's development. In order to ensure no miss or misinterpretation of essential requirements, deep understanding of the stakeholders' processes and interests is needed, as well as up to date information, since information changes within time.

Here, all stakeholders that are expected to be impacted by ChildRescue solution are recorded, both the ones that are envisioned to participate actively in the missing children investigation cause and the ones on which indirect impact is expected stemming from ChildRescue value proposition. These are people and organisations that are directly or indirectly involved in the value chain of the investigation and discovery of missing children. Below, in Table 2-1, lies an identification of such a broad range of stakeholders, grouped in meaningful categories and their mapping with the ChildRescue Platform's actors, as there are recognised and described in section 4.2 of this deliverable.

An initial stakeholders identification was first realised in a proposal basis, reported in the DoA, while the present categorisation is an update of that analysis.

Table 2-1 ChildRescue Stakeholders

Stakeholder group	Description	Relevant Actors
A. Missing children	Missing children are the target of the investigation mission, although not directly engaged in the ChildRescue solution.	Not an Actor. Considered as a special Actor; missing child.
B. Unaccompanied Migrant Minors	This group refers to all migrant children under the age of eighteen "who have been separated from both parents and other relatives and are not being cared for by an adult who, by law or custom, is responsible for doing so." ¹	Not an Actor. Considered as a special Actor; missing child.
C. Legal Guardians and caretakers	In this category, all people who have the legal authority (and the corresponding duty) to care	Not a direct Actor.

¹ <http://www.unhcr.org/40f646444.pdf>

(Parents, Facility Managers etc.)	for the personal and property interests of a minor (missing child or unaccompanied minor in the ChildRescue case) are considered. The members of this group are the ones responsible for the initiation of an investigation process, informing the authorities about their missing child.	Considered as a special Actor; Parent/Guardian/Relative of the missing child
D. Missing Children Response Organisations	In this group, all organisations that are occupied with the support of the investigation process of a missing child are considered. In Europe, this accounts for all members of the MCE Network, among which, SoC and CF.	Search & Rescue Team members, Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Network Manager, Organisation Coordinator, Facility Manager, Organisation Owner. Also "Organisation" as a special actor.
E. Unaccompanied Migrant Minors Care Organisations	All organisations that are dealing with the unaccompanied migrant children and their registration and care are part of this stakeholder group. RC represents this group in ChildRescue.	Hosting Facility Manager, Search & Rescue Team members, Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Network Manager, Organisation Coordinator Manager, Organisation Owner. Also "Organisation" as a special actor.
F. Other NGOs and Voluntary Organisations	Any other NGOs and Voluntary Organisations that do not fall into D and E categories, but they are offering, along with other actions and initiatives, their services in the investigation and identification of missing children are concentrated in this group. Any Search and Rescue Teams that do not belong in the Missing Children Investigation Organisations themselves (or E. category) are part of this group too.	Volunteer Team Member, Search & Rescue Team members, Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Network Manager, Organisation Coordinator Manager, Organisation Owner.
G. Governmental Organisations	Apart from the aforementioned organisations, there are also specific governmental agencies/organisations, such as specific ministries, that are responsible for handling such	Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Network Manager, Organisation Coordinator

		missing children cases. All such governmental agencies fall in this stakeholder category.	Manager, Organisation Owner.
H.	Public prosecutors	The prosecutor is the chief legal representative of the prosecution in countries with either the common law adversarial system, or the civil law inquisitorial system ² . Public prosecutors are discriminated from "G" stakeholder group since they play an essential role in missing children cases and especially the decision to issue an Amber Alert. Therefore, they are considered a separate stakeholder group that in many cases represents the government.	None or Simple User (indirect stakeholder)
I.	Other governmental or private collaborators	Any governmental, public or private organisations or individuals that could be of any help in the investigation of a missing child or an unaccompanied migrant minor (e.g. the fire department, security agencies, bus drivers, etc.) will be contacted and engaged in the investigation process.	Simple User, Volunteer Team Member
J.	Police/ Coast Guard	The police (or the Coast Guard in the case of a missing child near the sea) is the one responsible for searching for a missing child. ChildRescue-enabled insights are aspired to be used directly by the police to guide their investigation towards new, knowledge-based directions.	None or Simple User (indirect stakeholder)
K.	Citizens – Open, General public	The General Public is a core stakeholder for ChildRescue since ChildRescue aims to engage an as wide as possible audience to participate actively in the discovery of a missing child through the valuable information that citizens close to the place a child was lost may offer.	Visitor, Simple User.

Missing children, although in most cases are not expected to be users of the platform, they lie at the core of the ChildRescue solution, while all actions revolve around them for their health and care. In that sense, children are the most important stakeholder, but at the same time, since they are considered mainly when missing, the least involved user.

The parents, legal guardians and the close environment of a missing child are also an important stakeholder group with the expected benefits for them ranging from increased awareness and better monitoring of the investigation process for the missing children or the unaccompanied minors

² <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Prosecutor>

movement to improved, real-time contribution to the profiling of a missing child. These stakeholders will not necessarily be also users of the platform, but they are expected to provide the most valuable information (regarding physical appearance, social background, habits, mentality, etc.) to be included in ChildRescue platform and all parallel investigation activities running (e.g. Amber Alert).

Moving to Missing Children Response Organisations (D), Unaccompanied Migrant Minors Care Organisations (E) and other NGOs and Voluntary Organisations (E), they all represent main expected users of the platform with the intensity of their involvement depending on their activities around the missing children cause. Especially, for Missing Children Response Organisations and Unaccompanied Migrant Minors Care Organisations, ChildRescue aspires to be a new, innovative tool supporting and revolutionising their current procedures towards more effective, knowledge-driven and facilitated investigation processes. In the course of the project's duration, SoC, CF and RC will be the first organisations who will use and test ChildRescue developments. However, SoC and CF along with and under the coordination of MCE (representing 30 organisations from 24 European countries³) are expected to further disseminate project's results to other Missing Children Response Organisations and relevant contacts. For operations that involve humanitarian tracing activities and the cases of unaccompanied migrant minors where public authorities aren't involved RC will use its own operational model, which will still be compatible with ChildRescue.

Furthermore, governmental organisations that are responsible for missing children cases (such as ministries) are also an important stakeholder representing the government.

Furthermore, any public or private service providers that can be of any help to the investigation of missing children (e.g. bus drivers, security agents) fall under category "Other governmental or private collaborators" (I) and will be contacted to participate actively in ChildRescue and become one of its users and core stakeholders.

On what concerns the public prosecutor, he is the one representing the government in most of the important decisions to be taken. In particular, the prosecutor decides whether a Publicity action or an Amber Alert is to be issued. It needs to be noted that he can also act as the legal guardian for the case of unaccompanied migrant minors or if there is no other legal guardian in the case of a child's disappearance. Therefore, the prosecutor is definitely a stakeholder of the ChildRescue solution, distinguishing him from other governmental organisations and roles to highlight his distinct role in the missing children cases. The public prosecutor could be or not user of ChildRescue platform.

Police are a stakeholder of great importance, as the police lead the investigation of a missing child. Police officers could be users of the platform in order to be informed instantly when there is new information about a missing child's case; definitely with different access level than the general public. The same applies with the coast guard.

Finally, since ChildRescue solution is addressed also to the general public in order to engage them actively in the investigation of a missing child, according to their location, citizens and the general public is definitely a ChildRescue stakeholder and an important actor-user of the platform. In that view, the citizens are expected to have great influence on ChildRescue, since their use of the platform will determine the success of the project.

³ <http://missingchildreuneurope.eu/mediator/about>

As indicated, there will be several access levels on the platform, with different information to be shared on each case. A first analysis of the various platform's actor roles, that are determining the different access levels, can be found in section 4.2 of the present deliverable.

2.2 ChildRescue Approach for Requirements Elicitation

This chapter describes in detail the requirements elicitation approach that was followed. Some of the most popular methodologies used for requirements elicitation are the Waterfall and the Agile approach, derived from the software development life cycle models.

According to the waterfall model approach, once the waterfall model cycle is complete, it is expected that all the requirements will be thoroughly developed and described. It is a very rigid model including high risk and uncertainty. On the contrary, the agile model breaks the requirements elicitation approach into small incremental builds. It is a more adaptive model than the waterfall model, which entirely depends on the requirement analysis and planning done in the beginning of cycle.

Due to the structure of the ChildRescue WPs, the combination of the waterfall and the agile approach is highly suggested. Therefore, the project aims to maintain a balance between them, resulting in a hybrid model. This is deduced from the fact that, while most of the general requirements will be set early, they must also be open to modifications depending on the experience and feedback given by the end-users in the future, since it wouldn't be realistic to define in detail the majority of the project's requirements till M3, while the project's overall duration is 36 months.

Under these circumstances, this document could be called "alive", meaning that it will be modified and enriched by the course of months. The goal of D1.1 is the specification of a framework for the gathering of the requirements, on top of which more specific user and system requirements will be built during the course of the project. The combined model that was developed, allowed the gathering of the main requirements from all stakeholders early in the project's lifecycle, but also keeps the requirements list open to modifications as the project stakeholders become involved and get a better understanding of the project itself. Of course, that means that no radical changes can be made after a certain point.

Three techniques for gathering requirements, among others that exist today, were used:

1. Interviews were conducted with SoC, CF and RC which are the pilot partners of the consortium, that handle missing children cases or/and are engaged in the care of unaccompanied minors. The most common technique for gathering information is to interview the various stakeholders about the processes they follow and what they need to change. The participation of the technology partners in the interviews ensures that the derived stakeholder requirements will be transformed into generalised system requirements. Apart from the definition of the user requirements, a formalisation of the processes these organisations apply in their normal operations for the AS-IS scenarios is attempted, aiming to use it as the input for the derived TO-BE scenarios.
2. Questionnaires which are more informal and they are used to gather requirements from stakeholders in remote locations or those who will have minor input into the overall requirements.
3. Use cases: "A use case is a methodology used in system analysis to identify, clarify, and organise system requirements. The use case is made up of a set of possible sequences of interactions between systems and users in a particular environment and related to a particular goal. Since a use case can be thought of as a collection of possible scenarios related to a particular goal, indeed, the use case and

goal are sometimes considered to be synonymous"⁴. After conducting the interviews and analysing the questionnaires, two use cases are thoroughly described; the missing children emergency use case, and the discovery and identification of unaccompanied minors use case. The goal is to describe these use cases both as part of the AS-IS, as well as the TO-BE scenarios. The AS-IS scenarios will represent the current state of the processes that the pilot partners follow for missing children and unaccompanied minors' identification. Barriers and needs are elicited in this chapter. In the TO-BE scenarios, the innovation proposition of ChildRescue is clarified, highlighting the most significant changes with respect to the AS-IS scenarios.

Requirements Overview

ChildRescue primary ambition is not the substitution of the missing children response organisations existing methodologies and processes. It will be based on these methodologies, but it will also expand them, creating an innovative solution, speeding up the existing search and identification procedures of missing children.

Gathering the requirements is the first step to accomplish that, consisting of the business, stakeholder and system requirements.

Business requirements lie at the top level. Initially, the ChildRescue stakeholders' identification takes place through the questionnaires that were shared, while the objectives and the reasons for change are identified both through the questionnaires and through the interviews with the pilot partners.

Stakeholder requirements follow, where having the input from the questionnaires and the targeted interview conducted, the AS-IS and TO-BE scenarios could be developed. As a result, the detailed description of AS-IS and TO-BE scenarios is extremely important. These scenarios are divided into 4 sub-processes: Preparation and Profiling, Coordination and Collaboration, Action Stage, Archiving. Firstly, the AS-IS scenarios are extensively described, along with the identified challenges that ChildRescue has to deal with. Then, the TO-BE scenarios are presented. Subsequently, the end-user requirements are derived. As indicated, the AS-IS scenarios are the cornerstones of the requirements elicitation approach, because the TO-BE scenarios are based on them, and as a consequence, the gathered requirements are also directly dependent on them.

Finally, system requirements consist of a brief description of the platform that will be developed, the user stories and the use case scenarios. After the initial set of the requirements, user stories for each type of platform's actor were developed. "User stories are commonly used with agile methodology. A user story is a very high-level definition of a requirement, containing just enough information so that the developers can produce a reasonable estimate of the effort to implement it."⁵

Regarding the technical objectives, it is necessary to link the user requirements to technical requirements. As a result, a number of generalised requirements arose. Finally, the requirements backlog will be maintained during the project implementation in order to guide the research and development tasks.

⁴ <http://searchsoftwarequality.techtarget.com/definition/use-case>

⁵ <http://www.agilemodeling.com/artifacts/userStory.htm>

3 Stakeholders Requirements

3.1 The Missing Children Emergency Use Case

3.1.1 AS-IS scenario & Identified Challenges

The AS-IS scenarios and the corresponding identified challenges were created after conducting two interviews, in which standard questionnaires were also filled. The interviews were conducted with the pilot partners and missing children's response organisations; SoC (Greece) and Child Focus (Belgium) and their associates. The Child Focus interview was online, while the SoC's interview took place in their premises. The SoC's interview was conducted on 02/03/2018 and lasted about 5 hours, from 12:00 till 17:00. The Child Focus (CF) interview was conducted on 14/03/2018 and lasted about 2 hours, from 17:00 till 19:00.

The purpose of the SoC's and CF's interviews was to identify the steps of the investigation process they follow when a child is reported missing. It needs to be noted that this process pertains only to internal organisational process, while external organisational process, such as authorities' support, is outside the scope of this work.

All activities following the process input and preceding the process output define the boundaries of the missing children investigation process (MCIP). Therefore, the SoC's and CF's MCIP starting boundary is defined by the reception of a call regarding the disappearance of a child. The process ending boundary is defined by SoC's and CF's finding the missing child. In that sense, identification of the location of a missing child and his/her return to their legal guardians is the output of the process.

The process by which the Missing Children Organisations (MCOs) can be summarised in a generalised form in Figure 3-1 and Figure 3-2. Overall, it consists of the four identified steps (Preparation and Profiling, Coordination and Collaboration, Action and Archiving), but many of the steps taken can be considered to be going back and forth between them. Additional to the process, the MCO constantly provides support to the family of the missing child or the found child, even long after a case is closed. The concept of the entire process can be broken down to the following key states of a case:

1. A child is reported missing to the police and the MCO and information is collected and shared.
2. The authorities in charge of the case instruct the MCO to issue an alert or perform more private actions, by disseminating material or requesting cross border collaborations within the MCE network.
3. If Search & Rescue teams exist for the MCO and are available, the police might ask from them to run an operation on the field.
4. When and if a case is resolved, the dissemination material is retracted, and the case files are updated and archived.

Figure 3-1 MCO Missing Child Process Part 1

Figure 3-2 MCO Missing Child Process Part 2

The two organisations follow similar processes, with some differences concerning mainly how active their investigation is and how their volunteers are involved in the investigation process. Their processes and their similarities and differences are described in the following chapters.

3.1.1.1 Preparation and Profiling

Preparation

Child Focus (CF) operates the European Hotline for Missing Children 116000 in Brussels. The people who work at the emergency line are called *call managers* (or operators) and they just take the calls. They ask the main information about the disappearance. They have to be quick and efficient on the calls they respond to, in order to be sure that the line remains free for new incoming calls, in case there is a limited number of available call managers. When they have enough information about the case e.g. how old the child is, which police station works on the file, etc., they transfer this information to the

case managers, who are in charge of the call managers and they mainly have a relevant academic background, e.g. psychologists, social scientists etc. The case managers communicate with the *police*, the appointed *prosecutor*, and the *parents*. There are eight call managers who work on three shifts per day; two in each shift. There are ten case managers who work from 9:00 till 17:00, and one of them who is on call for all the rest of the day (from 17:00 till 9:00).

Smile of Child (SoC) has call centres in six places in Greece: Athens (Marousi and Kareas), Thessaloniki, Patra, Crete, Kavala. The centres are staffed with qualified personnel (i.e. social scientists and psychologists) and are equipped with hardware and software (ECAAS – European Child Alert Automated System).

SoC operates 3 lines on a 24/7 basis:

- The National Helpline for Children SOS 1056
- The European Hotline for Missing Children 116000
- The European Helpline 116111 for Children and Adolescents

For the facilitation of the actions of the organisation, the 6 call centres are interconnected. This results in:

- Minimising the call waiting time
- Strengthening the capacity to manage more requests / calls
- Better coordination of the officers of all lines
- Expansion of the human resources of all lines
- Reliability and elimination of technical problems through multiple redundancies.

The interconnection of the centres (nodes), which is crucial for SoC, was made with the use of IP MPLS technology. That gives the ability to:

- Social Workers, Sociologists and Psychologists can answer calls from anywhere in the network
- the 4 points (nodes) can communicate directly with each other

The 4 interconnected points (nodes) communicate directly, transferring data, images, and sound. This topology of the network (full mesh) gives two important advantages:

- nodes not interested in that kind of "circulation", are not burdened with traffic data
- if there is a problem with a node, the communication between the others is not affected.

In case of a network failure, there are always alternative routes to maximise the network's availability.

SoC has a main server, so SoC's employees across Greece have access to the same information concurrently. SoC has also activity and state monitors, which show statistics of the call centre, such as the average call waiting time, how many operators are currently on a line, how many lines are free to receive a call, etc.

Furthermore, due to a CRM system, if someone has called SoC in the past using the same number, a tab automatically opens and lists the details of the person who called and any information from a previous case. If the person calls from a different number, the operator searches the CRM for the name of the caller and brings up the same information.

Profiling

The Missing Children Investigation Process (MCIP) is activated when a child is reported missing. This applies to both organisations. The MCIP is activated, when:

- the parents call directly to SoC or Child Focus

- the parents go in person to an appropriate police station, report on their child's disappearance, and the police decides to call SoC or CF

In the first case, both SoC and CF, call operator/manager asks the parents to report on their child's disappearance to the police. Missing Children Organisations are only authorised to perform any action relating to a disappearance by the police. They then come in contact with the police department where the report was or is being made and share all the information they have on the disappearance.

In the second case, if the parents call SoC/CF after contacting the police, the organisations verify with the police that a report was made. SoC's/CF's call operator/manager records all the information given to them by the police. The police usually call SoC/CF to ask for their contribution to a case.

The call operator/manager requests the caller's information and contact details. The profiling phase follows, where all information about the missing child is gathered. SoC's/CF's call operator/manager requests from the caller as much information about the child as possible. Indicative data requested include: name, date of birth, physical description, eye colour, hair colour, scent, height, weight, last clothes wearing, the last place they had seen the child, the child's relationship with social media, etc. A child's recent photograph is also requested. The call operator saves these information in digital format on the CRM system. The questions asked depend on the details the caller/parents will give about the child. SoC's experts (Psychologists and Sociologists) work with the family of the missing child for collecting additional data to build an initial psychosocial profile of the missing child. It needs to be noted that there are certain situations/answers that may raise "red flags". For example, if a parent hesitates to answer about their child's age, it could mean that either the parent is in shock or the child is a victim of neglect. These are evaluated on the fly by the operators and are added to the case file. If needed, SoC/CF experts may also visit the child's relatives even from this early stage to provide counselling and support.

The case files are a chronologically ordered collection (physical or digital) of the material and the events that relate to it, including communication logs about the case (phone calls, emails, interviews etc.), documents exchanged with the police, prosecutors, other organisations etc.

Both SoC and CF do not employ any standardised profiling method to pinpoint locations on a map to perform investigations, although they do make predictions, based on their expertise and previous experiences. In this respect, they provide consultancy services to the police, while their role is to act as a bridge between the parents and the police, the public prosecutors and other involved public authorities.

3.1.1.2 Coordination and Collaboration

In this step, although both CF and SoC are the only organisations in their countries directly involved in the investigation of missing children cases, greater distinctions among the two organisations can be identified.

Based on the decision made by the police and/or the prosecutor in charge of the case, the missing children organisations crudely classify the cases to three levels, based on the level of publicity the investigation will have: private, public and Amber Alert. The **private** level of investigations has the minimum amount of information distribution, which excludes public broadcast, posters etc. Flyers may be distributed, and verbal information may be given, but only to previously specified individuals (tellers at super markets, garbage truck drivers, security companies' employees etc). The **public** level of investigations can include the broadcasting of information to news outlets, websites, social media, TV

and radio stations etc, posters in public places, but excludes mandatory public service announcements channels (highway signs, metro stations, mandatory broadcast by TV stations etc.). When an **Amber Alert** is raised, all available channels can be activated, and usually they all are by default.

CF is in contact with its volunteer network to perform actions like distributing flyers and putting up posters. The network of volunteers is organised by maintaining a list of local coordinators, each able to mobilise their team of volunteers. CF cooperates with a security company (Securitas). The company is contacted to provide services that relate to active cases. More on this is described in the Action stage.

CF also cooperates with other organisations, not NGOs, like the railway company, the subway company in Brussels, supermarkets, etc.

CF is also in regular contact with the police for updates applying a protocol where the police knows what information to share and vice versa. Communication between them is mostly done by phone and emails.

SoC, on the other side, cooperates with many organisations, being more involved in the investigation process.

When a child is reported missing, SoC informs the police Immediate Action service and the National Centre for Health Operations (E.K.EP.Y.), looking for missing children in hospitals, while also cooperates with the Electronic Crime Prosecution Division, to find out if the child has a social media account and possibly elicit useful information.

Among others, SoC/CF cooperates with Facebook to further disseminate missing child's information in a wider public. SoC also cooperates with Hellenic Red Cross Samaritans, Hellenic Rescue Team Attica and Hellenic Rescue Team Thessaloniki.

At Marousi, SoC has its centre of operations, where the coordination and contact with volunteer (search and rescue) teams takes place. SoC has been set up the «Thanasis Makris» Search and Rescue Team for missing children. The aim of this volunteer group is the active investigation in urban or non-urban environments to locate children who have gone missing. All Search & Rescue team members are trained regularly. Key members of Missing Children Search and Rescue Team «Thanasis Makris» are the Canine Teams participating. The Canine Teams (handler and dog) are the only ones in Greece certified by the international NSARDA body (National Search and Rescue Dog Association UK) and the only Canine Teams in Greece, seeking a particular person. The Canine Teams look for a person, based on the person's own scent. Their response time is less than 24 hours, after the request for their assistance. To the accomplishment of its project, the Search and Rescue Team for Missing Children «Thanasis Makris» has at its disposal a Mobile Operations Unit and other vehicles (jeeps, ATV, motor vehicle, ambulances). If the child has disappeared near the sea, where the coast guard is responsible, then SoC cooperates with them as with the police. The General Secretariat for Civil Protection under the Ministry of Public Order & Citizen Protection is also able to mobilise local actors in case of a child's disappearance, e.g. inform the local garbage truck drivers to be alert.

As far as the cross-border cooperation, SoC and CF collaborate also with Missing Children Europe (MCE), as members of it, and all its members in case there are indications that a child that has gone missing may have crossed their countries' borders towards other countries.

3.1.1.3 Action Stage

As already mentioned, SoC/CF may be informed for the case by either the police or the parents themselves and police are responsible for finding the missing child.

In both SoC's and CF's case, call manager/operator speaks with the parents or anyone who provides information about the case, without, however, a fixed questionnaire. Their personnel is efficiently trained to handle such cases and ask specific, appropriate questions.

SoC/CF also receive calls from people that claim to have seen the missing child. In SoC's case, after an appropriate set of questions, if the testimony about the missing child is considered reliable, the information is kept and the police is called to inform them. Then, SoC notifies the police department of missing persons, sending a document with the information it received from the call. The phone calls are not being recorded from SoC, and if someone calls SoC, he/she is not obliged to give his personal information and SoC in any case does not save his/her personal details. This is a distinction from CF, that records the conversations of all the incoming calls, while the callers know that the conversations are recorded.

As far as social media is concerned, if the child has a public Facebook or other social media account, SoC's and CF's employees monitor the activity in these accounts and informs the police, in case of an event that inspires concern. Both SoC and CF have social media accounts to contribute to their purpose. In particular, SoC has a Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, YouTube and LinkedIn account and CF a Facebook and a Twitter account.

SoC uses two ways to publicise the missing child's disappearance. The first action is "Publicity" and the second action is "Amber Alert". These two actions are activated with the written consent of the guardian(s) or the legal representative(s). The public prosecutor, however, has the right of Amber Alert activation regardless the consent of the child's guardians. The prosecutor is the person who is in charge of the case file. If activation of Amber Alert is decided by the prosecutor, the police contact SoC/CF in order to activate the Amber Alert. The police and the public prosecutor decide the activation time of Publicity and Amber Alert.

CF uses both private and public methods to find a missing child. When CF handles children runaways, it uses private actions. For example, in case of a teenager's runaway, CF, along with the other investigation actions, activates also private broadcast, e.g. flyers. As an example, they leverage their collaboration with supermarkets, asking its employees to hide their flyers of the missing child and inform CF and police, if they see the child. For a private broadcast, CF does not need the request of the prosecutor. It is not a must have, but it is nice to have. For the public broadcast, CF needs the request of the prosecutor, just like SoC's case. CF keeps track of the locations where posters and flyers were handed out or put up, so that they can be collected after the case is closed for the protection of the children's privacy. CF also maintains a list of local coordinators. If a decision is made to focus the distribution of information to a specific area, the network manager contacts the coordinator there who contacts his team of volunteers for the distribution of the flyers/posters.

For both SoC and CF, the necessary information for the activation of Amber Alert are shared by the police via email. These organisations do not need formal request from the police. This happens in order to be as efficient as possible. After the Amber Alert or Publicity activation, the rest of the paperwork is filled.

In the Publicity action, a poster is uploaded on SoC's/CF's social media, on SoC's/CF's official website, and on other websites that SoC/CF cooperates with. Moreover, a poster is sent with a press release to various TV stations. In Belgium, the TV stations are obliged to present the child's disappearance, whereas in Greece, it is at the TV stations' discretion to present it, e.g. as a subject in the news, or on a TV show. This comes in contrast with the Amber Alert action. CF creates posters and CF's volunteers

distribute them in order to be seen either locally or nationally. These posters are only removed when the child is found. A case file is maintained to record the places where posters are placed and collect them when the case is closed. This action is less massive than the Amber Alert.

The poster that is used in both "Publicity" and "Amber Alert" actions should have the following information: recent photo of the child, name, age, disappearance date and place, hair and eye colour, height, weight, a brief description of what the child was wearing the day of disappearance, special characteristics, health issues. In the past, in case of parental abduction the poster contained a photo of both the child and their father. In case, there are two siblings or friends that were together and are missing, the poster may contain two photos and descriptions of them. This is decided case by case. Both Publicity and Amber Alert actions contain the same information.

Amber Alert is a National Coordinating Programme of timely and accurate notification of citizens on cases of missing/abducted minors. The operation of the Amber Alert is based on the provision of quick, accurate and detailed information to citizens on a missing child case few minutes after the reporting of the case to the police or the SoC/CF. To achieve this, a number of actors (public private, voluntary) are involved with the purpose to communicate the details of the missing child and other basic information through the mass media (TV channels and radio spots), social media (Facebook posts), SMS, announcements on airports' monitors, subways etc. In Greece, today, there are 61 partners participating in Amber Alert, initiated by SoC in 2007. Amber Alert -currently- operates through the coalition of 61 bodies.

It needs to be noted that special attention is needed when activating an Amber Alert, since risks for the child may rise. As an example, a child may leave on his own and decide to come back after a few days, but be scared of that due to the activation of Amber Alert. Therefore, decision on Amber Alert's activation should be careful and meet some of the following criteria:

- Small age of child / children
- Clear indications that the life or health of the child may be at risk.
- Suspicions that indicate a possible abduction or kidnapping of a child.
- The activation of the system will help to identify the child

The activation process of Amber Alert is the following:

At first, a SoC's expert logs in in the European Child Alert Automated System (ECAAS); CF's expert logs in a Belgian platform respectively. They fill in the necessary information of the missing child, e.g. recent photo of the child, name, age, disappearance date and place, hair and eye colour, height, weight, a brief description of what the child was wearing when last seen, special characteristics, health issues. There is an upper limit on the letters that can be used.

After 6-7 minutes, the system develops all the available file formats, e.g. video spot, radio spot, posters, mp4, pdf, jpg, xml, etc. Then the SoC's/CF's operator/manager checks the correctness of the data on the generated files. After they are sure about the correctness of the data of the missing child, they send the appropriate files to the partners who participate in the Amber Alert action. Each partner doesn't receive all the file formats, but the ones which fit in their system. Additionally, an email is sent to them in order to inform them that information have been sent.

In Belgium, Amber Alert's initial duration is 3 hours, unless police, after the prosecutor's confirmation, tell CF to stop Amber Alert earlier than that. Then, the police, after the prosecutor's request, makes a new debriefing and tells CF, to have Amber Alert activated, e.g. for 3 hours more or until they find the

missing child. In any case, the prosecutor has to give confirmation every 3 hours, else CF stops to transmit the Amber Alert in Belgium.

In Greece, Amber Alert's initial duration is 48 hours, unless police tell SoC to stop Amber Alert earlier than that. Then, the police make a new debriefing and tell SoC, to have Amber Alert activated, e.g. for 24 hours more or until they find the missing child. The decision about this time extension is made by the prosecutor.

When police notify SoC/CF to stop Amber Alert, then SoC/CF send a press release to notify the partners who participate to Amber Alert to stop broadcasting it. In order to be sure, SoC/CF calls the partners to ensure they received the notification to stop its broadcasting.

In case of a cross-border collaboration, two types of cooperation can be identified.

The first is when a foreign country asks SoC/CF to broadcast a disappearance. In that case, they don't have to ask the prosecutor to broadcast the disappearance, but they have to be sure that their colleagues of the foreign countries have their prosecutor's permission.

The second kind is when the child disappeared from Belgium/Greece, and they believe that the missing child is in another country. In case there are indications that the child is abroad, SoC/CF informs the police about these indications. If they want to broadcast the disappearance in a foreign country, they have to request the prosecutor's permission. Then, SoC/CF which is a Missing Children Europe(MCE) member, contact MCE, in order to examine if there is the possibility of collaboration with the other country's organisations, filling in a transnational form which is sent to the corresponding organisation(s) - MCE members - of the country(ies) where the child may be.

Finally, as far as active search is concerned, SoC does have active investigation in the field, while CF does not have (as also the protocol that CF has with the justice department and the police explicitly indicates).

In particular, CF's volunteer network's actions are restricted to sharing and distributing flyers, and putting up posters, while it also calls the security company it collaborates with (i.e. Securitas) when they need them, providing them all necessary information about the missing child and its location when lost. In this sense, in their normal daily operations of patrolling areas, houses and businesses, Securitas also pay attention for the child that disappeared, and CF looks for.

SoC activates active search upon request by the authorities in charge of the operations to perform an active investigation. Then, the operator of the operational centre is mobilised, and sends an SMS from a SoC's platform to the volunteers to find out what their availability is. Then, all available volunteers gather in order to help find the missing child. If there are indications, that the child may be in a specific area, then SoC prints flyers, which are distributed there. Creation of posters and flyers takes place in order to be distributed in patrol cars throughout the country for the discreet search of the missing child. These flyers contain the same information as Publicity and Amber Alert actions. Moreover, when asked, Missing Children Search and Rescue Team «Thanasis Makris» are also engaged in coordination with the authorities to search for the child in the specified area. The Canine teams of the Search and Rescue team are also activated and wherever they are needed, they go by car and using the mobile operational unit, which is equipped with a geo-tracking system of the team members. Rescue team members communicate via CB or mobile phones between them and the mobile operations unit or the operator on the centre of operations. Whatever information they receive, they also inform the police security

department and the SoC's department. The Rescue Team is dismissed only if the child is found or if the police end the operation for any reason. When the child is found, SoC records all the information from the volunteers, what went well, what went wrong and updates the case file.

3.1.1.4 Archiving

For SoC/CF, a case is closed only when the child is found. This means that SoC/CF never stops trying to trace a missing child. CF keeps the case files in digital format, while SoC keeps its case files in digital but also in printed format. This happens, because part of the SoC's communication with the police is done by fax.

When a case is closed, the file of the missing child is updated, with all the actions that were done. SoC/CF handle the case's closure in a secure and privacy-respectful manner. When a case is closed, the data are not subject to changes.

SoC/CF stays in touch with the parents in order to provide psychological support, advisory support and sessions with a psychologist, in case they agree with that.

From a statistical perspective, it is interesting to notice that SoC handled in 2016, 170 child disappearances. Of these, Publicity action was activated for 47 children and Amber Alert was activated for 9 children. For 12 children the "Thanasis Makris" team was activated. 80% of children were identified. CF mostly activates 1 Amber Alert per year. In 2016, they handled 1720 disappearances. Private or public actions were activated for about 100 of them. For half of them a private action was activated and for the rest half a public action was activated.

In order to improve their operations, CF keeps statistics data about the age of the child, the duration of the disappearance, the location of the disappearance, if the case was worrisome or not, if the teenager runaway from a shelter, an institution or not, etc. They also do an annual report with this information.

SoC publishes statistical analyses on April, June, and December each year. These analyses contain information about the number of SoC's cases, what the age of the missing children is, what was their sex, how many publicity actions and Amber Alert actions were activated, etc. On the International Missing Children's Day, May 25th, SoC also publishes statistical analysis about SoC's cases.

3.1.2 TO-BE scenario

ChildRescue purpose is not to change and reorganise the current process that SOC/CF follow, which is shown in Figure 3-1 and Figure 3-2, but to work in parallel with their process. The ChildRescue platform will work complementarily to the existing missing children investigation process. Its ambition is a solution towards the direction of reducing the time needed for locating the child. Time is the worst enemy in missing children cases; the first hours are the most decisive, as traces are lost afterwards, so time is precious. Moreover, ChildRescue will improve the problems faced by the process, such as volunteers' coordination, insufficient capture and diffusion of information, etc. It will also facilitate the process and improve the record keeping and sharing of information.

3.1.2.1 Preparation and Profiling

In order to capture and diffuse the information easier, when a child is missing, the case file will be added to the platform. The case file will include personal and psychosocial information about the child and information mined from the social media profiles and activities of the child for identifying activity

and mobility patterns. In this way ChildRescue will integrate a mechanism that makes use and merges all available sources of information.

Of course, people in charge decide the course of the investigation, but ChildRescue will offer an additional tool that can be used. That is the suggestion of possible locations the missing child may be, based on algorithms which elicit data combining multiple sources, such as: means of transport routes and schedules that the missing person had a fairly convenient access to, knowledge extraction from social media account analysis, pattern matching of similar past cases, places recently visited, interests, etc. With the contribution of several algorithms and the predictive analytics methods that will be used, ChildRescue will suggest e.g. a geographic region that the missing child may reach. This input will be taken into consideration from the people in charge and they will decide what the next steps would be in the investigation, not the platform. The ChildRescue platform will not make any decisions in a sense that it will produce any automatic decisions.

ChildRescue could also enhance the procedure of profiling by providing indexing functionalities which will allow easier and more efficient retrieval of information. Automatic association between similar profiles and the corresponding cases' metadata can also be derived during profiling by ChildRescue. Any significant correlation will be highlighted and evaluated by the operation centre operator.

As far as the additional assistance that social media could provide in the profiling stage, it is not possible to have people monitor in a 24-hour base Facebook or other social media accounts of missing children, in case there is an update on their accounts. ChildRescue could solve that problem in a technical way, for example, when a missing child's profile is updated, the case manager will receive a notification. This action could be valuable in case of a child's runaway, a useful information from a newly created post which had not been taken into account before, etc. Since direct access to the account might not be available, only public posts may be tracked.

Furthermore, despite that the users of the platform will get almost the same amount of information as they do today when an alert is issued, ChildRescue will speed up the way this information is going to be shared. This will happen because this information will be centralised, and the case manager will massively send it to the relevant stakeholders that look for the missing child. The information distribution will be instant via the platform and the search for the missing child will be constantly updated. Of course, each stakeholder will have different access level to the given information, as described in section 4.2 of the present deliverable.

On the other hand, not only the distribution but also the collection of information will be faster. In case a citizen is conscious of the location or any other clue for the missing child, they will be able to easily submit it to the ChildRescue mobile application along with potential evidence (e.g. photo, testimonial) and tags (e.g. for the missing child's condition that enhance the profiling information).

3.1.2.2 Coordination and Collaboration

During the coordination phase, ChildRescue will provide better communication and collaboration between the volunteer teams, notifying and giving them guidelines accordingly. Instant online communication with volunteers will also be established.

Concerning the volunteers' coordination, the leaders of each volunteers' team will get instructions by their organisation with the police's guidance and will have the ability to instantly make a request to the team members to take part in the investigation and be informed about their availability. Through the platform the leader will be able to guide his team's members in real-time. The volunteers' coordination

will be instant and easier. The members of the teams in the field will also have the potential to communicate with other volunteers and the community, in a privacy-aware manner, in order to make necessary arrangements and exchange ideas through a transparent, uninterrupted information flow.

Additionally, ChildRescue will make it more convenient and efficient to manage cross-border cases. In these cases, there will be direct sharing of the case file with another country's MCE member through the platform.

3.1.2.3 Action Stage

Regarding the public dissemination of the child's disappearance case, one of the key features that ChildRescue adds to the current process are the notifications that will be sent to the smartphones of the ChildRescue platform users. ChildRescue aspires to make every citizen a social investigation sensor who actively contributes to the identification of missing children whenever identified near their current location. The notifications will be sent to all the ChildRescue users that are near the area a child disappeared or might be after their disappearance. The direct line of location-based communication with the users of the mobile application can increase the attentiveness of the users to the cases that are closest to them. The fact that the location-based notifications will help locate the missing child faster than the traditional methods and reduce the number of alerts displayed to the end users will both increase the protection of the privacy of the missing child. ChildRescue will provide geo-fencing distribution of information, and the engagement of the users receiving the notifications. For example, a child is lost in the centre of Athens. At first, the notifications could be sent to ChildRescue users in the centre of Athens and around it. As time passes, the radius could be set to be increasing algorithmically. The shape of the areas will stem from suggestions made by the predictive algorithms, but ultimately will be selected by the coordinators of the operation.

Today, there is information bombardment coming from many sources, e.g. internet, social networks, e-mails, TV, websites, radio, newspapers, etc. It would not be desirable to spam ChildRescue users with constant alerts, as this would cause an opposite result to the wanted. In order to avoid this, ChildRescue users will not receive many notifications per year, as this would be daunting. Last year, 9 Amber Alerts were raised in Greece and 1 in Belgium. Of course, these disappearance cases did not happen in the same area. Consequently, the notifications that will be sent to the ChildRescue users per year will be counted on the fingers of one hand. Thus, the notifications will not annoy them, but they will achieve their purpose, motivating users to read the notifications, as they will not constantly be sent. This will be achieved because there will be location focused distribution of the alerts.

Furthermore, today when there is the Publicity or Amber Alert Action activated, people have to remember the picture of the missing child and the details about their disappearance, something that it is very easy to forget. With ChildRescue, users will have a reference to see the details of the disappearance and the picture of the child as many times they want. This will be extremely helpful in cases where a user may see a child that resembles to the missing child and wants to cross-check it. It is very simple and fast to open the app and do so. Then if the user believes that this is the missing child, they contact with the ChildRescue operation centre and shares this information. Otherwise, the user may not remember the child and a useful testimony is omitted.

3.1.2.4 Archiving

When the case is closed, ChildRescue will securely handle it and in a privacy-respectful manner. Semantic annotation of the documentation and lessons learnt of the case will be provided internally in

order to support its retrieval in case of similar cases in the future. Additional functionalities that enable the easier aggregation of past data and the derivation of analytics will be provided so that the missing children organisation's users will be able to access and manipulate past knowledge and data via a central dashboard. In the case of the mobile application towards the community, all data related to the specific case are erased from the citizens' devices, leaving behind only the non-personal information, statistics and outcome of the specific case.

3.1.3 Derived User Requirements

The ChildRescue platform is aiming at reinforcing the SoC through all stages of a missing child's investigation, by providing a multifunctional environment that will enable the fast and trustworthy diffusion of valuable information about the case. Its' purpose is to enhance all users participating in the operations and facilitate the already existing processes of the organisations and the responsible authorities, but not necessarily to transform them. The needed and desirable provisions of a tool like ChildRescue can be elicited from the descriptions of potential situations and the actions followed from the SoC, as presented in the AS-IS scenarios. Improvement potential is considered in the TO-BE scenarios, alongside with solutions to existing difficulties. After taking into consideration both the AS-IS and the TO-BE scenarios, we have shaped the derived user requirements of ChildRescue for the SoC, although they are not yet strictly defined. These user requirements will be revisited and further refined while the project progresses.

In Table 3-1, all the derived user requirements are presented, grouped by the 4 sub-processes, with few belonging to core functionality. The user groups are mapped according to the ChildRescue Platform's actors as described in Table 4-5 of this deliverable and denote the active side of each requirement.

Table 3-1 Derived User Requirements for the Missing Children Emergency Use Case

#	Sub-Process	Requirement Description	User group (related Actors)
1	Core	Registration to the ChildRescue platform.	All
2	Core	Different access level and privileges for each user group.	All
3	Preparation/ Profiling	Ability to upload case files to the platform, including information from multiple sources (personal details, psychosocial reports, social media profiles) about the child.	Organisation Case Manager
4	Preparation/ Profiling	Easily retrieve information and patterns or correlations pertaining to the specific case and to past similar cases and profiles.	Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Coordination Manager
5	Preparation/ Profiling	Receive suggestions by the system on possible Points of Interest regarding the child. The POIs could be calculated based on testimonies, historical data (if any) and social media preferences and past activity analysis.	Organisation Case Manager

6	Preparation/ Profiling	Fast collection of information from all users that actively participate in the investigation and can enhance the profiling process.	Organisation Case Manager
7	Preparation/ Profiling	Fast distribution of the available profiling information to all relevant Stakeholders to the investigation of the missing child. The amount of information received will be defined by each user access rights.	Organisation Case Manager, Volunteer Team Member, Search & Rescue Team member, Organisation Network Manager, Simple User
8	Collaboration/ Coordination	Improve the communication and data exchange between SoC and citizens by providing more means of interaction (e.g. mobile app, case collaboration space)	Organisation Case Manager, Simple User
9	Collaboration/ Coordination	Improve the communication and information exchange between the Organisation and Volunteer/Rescue teams using a real-time collaboration space	Organisation Case Manager, Volunteer Team Member, Search & Rescue Team member, Organisation Network Manager
10	Collaboration/ Coordination	Teams can notify their team members for participation in a new investigation operation and check their availability	Volunteer Team Member, Search & Rescue Team member
11	Collaboration/ Coordination	Better communication and collaboration among members of the same team and among teams. Real-time guidance by team leaders.	Volunteer Team Member, Search & Rescue Team member
12	Collaboration/ Coordination	Improve cross-border and international cooperation with other Amber Alert national entities, or with other organisations/ NGOs.	Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Network Manager, Organisation Coordinator, Organisation Owner
13	Collaboration/ Coordination	Ability to reach out to citizens and simple users and ask for their feedback based on their location	Organisation Staff
14	Action Stage	Increase search and rescue teams efficiency by having their members share their position in a real-time map	Search & Rescue Team Member
15	Action Stage	Enhance the monitoring of each case's progress and create suggestions about future steps (routes to follow, POIs to search)	Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Network Manager
16	Action Stage	Users may share (anonymously or not) potential evidence (multimedia files, location data) in case they think they have traced the missing child or have any other piece of information	Simple User, Visitor, Volunteer Team Member

17	Action Stage	Users will get location-based notification alerts and updates and may receive potential evidence in order for it to be crowd-validated	Simple User, Visitor, Volunteer Team Member, Search & Rescue Team member
18	Archiving	Cases are closed in a privacy-respectful manner and are semantically annotated for easier retrieval.	Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Coordinator
19	Archiving	Past cases are available for analysis and pattern matching with current cases.	Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Coordinator
20	Archiving	After closure of a case, all sensitive private data will be removed from the platform and public access/users' devices. Only statistics and non-personal data could remain public.	Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Coordinator

3.2 Discovery and Identification Use Case of Unaccompanied Minors

3.2.1 AS-IS scenario & Identified Challenges

The AS-IS scenario and the corresponding identified challenges were created after an interview with the pilot partner and Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minors organisation, RC. The interview took place in the premises of RC, at Likavittou 1, 10672, Athens, Greece. It was conducted on 01/03/2018 and lasted about 5 hours, from 10:00 till 15:00.

The subject of the interview was about the RC's processes:

1. The accommodation centres and the social services provided to the unaccompanied minors,
2. The Tracing department's operations to restore family links.

The purpose of the RC's interview was to identify the steps of the process that RC follows. Since there is no standardisation of these processes, an effort was made to find what parts of it can be put down to paper as business processes. The boundary for both the interviews and the described processes is the actions taken by RC, since they will be the users active stakeholders of ChildRescue. All other processes are either briefly described or are presented as black boxes of external input.

RC operates three accommodation **UMC centres** and one **safe zone** program in Greece. The UMC centres are in Athens, Kalavryta and Volos and the safe zone program is in Ritsona.

RC started operating the UMC centre in Athens on July 2017. It has been providing hospitality to thirty (30) unaccompanied migrant children up till today. It provides the following services:

- Provision of food and accommodation
- Counselling and psychosocial support both in individual and group level
- Interpretation / mediation to community agencies
- Accompany to asylum services and hospitals
- Intercultural and recreational activities

The UMC Accommodation centre in Kalavryta is been operated since July 2017. Up till today, has provided hospitality to 27 unaccompanied migrant children, aged mainly between 15 and 18 years old. The majority of them are mostly from Pakistan, Afghanistan, Syria, Bangladesh, Algeria.

Up till today, the UMC Accommodation centre in Volos has provided hospitality to 1,358 unaccompanied migrant children, aged mainly between 15 and 18 years old. The majority of them are mostly from Pakistan, Afghanistan, Syria, Bangladesh, Algeria. The centre has been operating since 2008.

The safe zone program was launched in May 2017. The capacity of the project is for 30 unaccompanied migrant children and up till today it has been providing accommodation to 95 unaccompanied migrant children. The main objectives of the project are:

- Meeting the basic subsistence needs of the migrant children (safety, food, hygiene etc.),
- Facilitation of their access to health care services (vaccination, medical check-up, escort to the hospitals),
- Educational activities, creative activities, provision, legal support (in cooperation the International Organisation for Migration (IOM)), cultural mediation/interpretation, psychosocial support.

RC operates the 2105140440 Hotline. It is on from Monday to Friday from 8.00 a.m. until 20.00 pm. Specially trained employees answer the calls they receive in the following languages: Greek, English, French, Arabic, Kurdish, Farsi, Pashtu, Dari, Russian, Swahili, Kinyarwanda, Kirundi. It provides:

- Information on refugees and asylum seekers (asylum procedure, residence permit, legal issues, etc.)
- Information on agencies, services and their respective benefits
- Mediation and facilitation of agencies and services
- Interpreting by telephone
- Support and directions

The RC's **Tracing Service (TS)**, that handles the tracing cases, is not only active in unstable situations; in time of war and peace the TS traces missing persons, both in Greece and abroad, but it also facilitates communication between dispersed family members, including migrants and refugees. Its goals are:

- Maintain family unity
- Restore family links
- Restore and maintain communication among family members
- Trace the missing persons and inform their relatives

The RC's Tracing Service has the largest tracing record in Greece and one of the largest worldwide, with 4.500.000 personal files. The "Information Bank" of the Tracing Service is constantly fed with new data and documents while, for more effective function, it collaborates closely with the International Committee of Red Cross (ICRC), the International Network of Tracing Services, State or Private Institutions, International Organisations, Mass Media and volunteers both in Greece and abroad. Its activities are:

- Collect personal data of sought persons from their immediate family members (enquirers)
- Keep record of and processing the data of the sought/missing persons and of the enquirers
- Gather and keep record of general information
- Restore and maintain communication after having traced the missing persons
- Provide Red Cross Messages (RCM)
- Contribute to the repatriation of victims of armed conflicts (under IHL provisions)
- Provide assistance to Greeks living abroad and to foreigners living in Greece to trace their relatives in cooperation with local or foreign institutions, governmental or non-governmental organisations (NGOs)
- Provide certificates to hostages, prisoners, tortured, murdered, in order to help the victims or their relatives on retirement issues or on their rehabilitation.

The activities of the RC's Tracing Service are based on the right of families to stay united and the right of the people to be informed about the fate of their beloved ones and reunite with them, expand further than just tracing people. The Mandate of the Tracing Service is "to maintain the family unity", while tracing is done always with respect to the dignity and the right to privacy.

The placement process initiates when a child comes to a RC's accommodation centre for unaccompanied minors or when a placement order is received. The tracing process starts when the RC's Tracing Department receives a request for tracing a person by an immediate relative or a legal guardian.

For the first process, the starting boundary is defined by the time an unaccompanied minor is placed in a RC's accommodation centre. The process's ending boundary is when the minor is no longer under RC's care. For the second process, the starting boundary is the moment there is a tracing request with

the RC Tracing Service placed by an immediate family member. The process's ending boundary is when the sought person is found and if found alive, communication between the person seeking and the person sought is restored. The Red Cross Movement fully respects individuals' right to privacy, in the regard the details of located persons might be released to enquirers only with their consent.

The extracted data from each process is the output of the two processes.

The two processes (Accommodation of Unaccompanied Minors and the Tracing service) can be summarised in Figure 3-3 and Figure 3-4 accordingly. The first process can be broken down to the following states:

1. A placement order is issued and the unaccompanied minor arrives at the hosting facility (shelters, safe zone). The necessary documents (personal identification form, social history) are filled by the facility's social service.
2. Counting of the minors happens every morning and evening in the facility.
3. If someone is missing the Police, Public Prosecutor (PP), EKKA, Ministry of Migration Policy (MoMP) are informed about the minor's voluntary departure.
4. If the minor returns to the facility within 1 day of departure, PPEM are informed that the minor returned. If not, PPEM are informed that the minor is not included in the capacity of the shelter and thus, there is a vacancy in the facility.
5. Case is closed when the minor becomes an adult and leaves the shelter, relocated or reunited with their families.

The second process can be broken down to the following states:

1. The Tracing department receives a request for tracing a person; the tracing request form is filled out.
2. If the enquirer is an unaccompanied minor or there are indications that the sought person might be dead, additional documents are filled. If there is information about a large-scale accident, e.g. shipwreck, the tracing department receives additional documents regarding the accident.
3. Communication effort is made with family members.
4. Volunteers' activation and field work can be activated after the previous step or in case there is a natural disaster and children are missing from the organisation's facility.
5. Case is administratively closed 3 years after the initial request, when all means of research have been exhausted (negative closure) or when the sought person is found (positive closure).

Figure 3-3 Accommodation of Unaccompanied Minors

Figure 3-4 The Tracing Service

3.2.1.1 Preparation and Profiling

Accommodation of Unaccompanied Minors

All foreign national or stateless persons below the age of 18, who either arrive in the EU unaccompanied by a responsible adult or are left unaccompanied after their arrival, are considered unaccompanied minors. Most of them come from countries at war and/or poor living conditions.

An unaccompanied minor is located for the first time on the entry points (hot spots) to be registered by the national authorities (police), the asylum service of Ministry of Migration Policy, the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR). At the same time, tests are conducted to detect if the minor is less than 18 years old. For example, an underage minor can be identified by using forensic (dental and bone) age estimation methods.

After the registration process, the unaccompanied minor is given priority, in relation to the adults, to leave the hot spots and move to the mainland. In most cases, unaccompanied minors are transferred to protective custody (structures inside the police departments). Then, they are usually transported to intermediate structures called "safe zones", and after three months, to a permanent hosting facility. This happens after a placement order is issued. The placement order is issued for safe zone program by the Ministry of Migration Policy and for the shelters by the National Centre for Social Solidarity (EKKA). EKKA has the national hosting facilities management. It has the overall supervision and coordination of all hosting facilities, e.g. how many vacancies have the hosting facilities, which unaccompanied minor goes to one or the other hosting facility, etc.

When the placement order is issued, the Ministry of Migration Policy or EKKA sends an e-mail and the relevant documents to the organisation running the facility (in this case and hereafter the Hellenic Red Cross (RC)), and to RC's HQ to inform them about the unaccompanied minor's placement. Sometimes, due to lack of vacancies in the permanent hosting facilities, the minor remains more than three months in the safe zone. A public prosecutor is appointed as the legal guardian of the unaccompanied minor.

When the placement is made, the hosting facility receives additional to the placement legal documentation regarding the minor, either from the reception centre, a previous hosting facility, or from the police, where the unaccompanied minor was located beforehand. These documents are copies of the police service note (identity of the unaccompanied minor) and the asylum seeker card (if it exists) that the minor has in their possession. The police service note contains data such as: photograph, citizenship, sex, name, surname, father's name, mother's name, date of birth, if the minor has passport or not, information about the place where the minor will be hosted.

Hosting facilities also keep a record of the current occupancy state, including the list of minors accommodated and the vacancies it has, which is updated when an unaccompanied minor is received in a hosting facility. The staff informs the unaccompanied minor about the processes that the facility follows and the risks they face. The social services of the facility fill in the social history form by interviewing the minor. The form contains profiling information that will help identify risks to the wellbeing of the minor or his environment, or the possibility that the minor will leave the facility by his own accord (voluntary departure), usually without informing anyone. Some of the indications for high-risk cases or possibility of voluntary departure are: an age under 15 years, lack of interest in activities, difficulties adapting to the new environment, distant or aggressive behaviour, declaration that another country or city is their final destination, history or reports of receiving violence and sexual and/or psychological abuse, being marginalised in the reception classes they attend, being pushed into

delinquent behaviour etc. Many of these minors have psychological issues stemming from prolonged exposure to conditions of war, physical and/or sexual violence and exploitation, drug use and prostitution. Early assessment of the special needs of a minor is vital to provide appropriate accommodation and support, as well as to predict possible outcomes of the person's stay at the facility. The possible negative outcomes that need to be predicted and prevented are trafficking, abuse, violence, exploitation, lack of care for health issues, either psychiatric or physical, including chronic diseases and other.

Further to the information collected in this stage, social media accounts of the minor are requested. If they do not have one, they are suggested to create one (tracing procedure) as a mechanism for the prevention of disappearances and their protection. It has been observed that most of the communication between the minors and their families is done through social media, and NGOs commonly using them to keep in touch with the minors, even after they leave their care, as they are reliable as a means of communication than mobile phones, since they can change SIM cards after they leave the country. The social service also notes, if the unaccompanied minor has any friends from other hosting facilities, especially if the unaccompanied minor was staying to another hosting facility in the past; since there are some cases when unaccompanied minors leave the hosting facility without notifying the personnel, to visit friends in other hosting facilities.

Five days after the unaccompanied minor's arrival to the facility, the "Best Interest Assessment (BIA)" form is filled in by the social service of the facility. BIA contains information about the unaccompanied minor, such as: current participation in education activities, additional vulnerability (unaccompanied child, separated child, disabilities, risk of trafficking or exploitation, psychological issues, medical health issues, early marriage, mental health issues, risk of actual abuse, etc.).

These files are kept at the RC's hosting facility. Each RC's hosting facility has its own files and records on the unaccompanied minors it accommodates or accommodated in the past. There is no centralised organisation-wide, country-wide, or international database for storing these data, and every institution keeps its own records. Some of these files are in paper form, others are digital files.

Every morning and evening, the residents of the facility are counted. If a minor is missing, it is automatically considered as a "voluntary departure".

The Tracing Service

The main activities regarding the search for a missing or unaccounted for person are performed by the tracing service or under its coordination. In general, tracing refers to activities involving the restoration of family links, where a person is looking for another person, who isn't necessarily legally missing or in danger. When communication is restored or is deemed impossible, the tracing procedure ends.

The RC's Tracing Service opens tracing cases and initiate a tracing procedure only on the ground of an individual request for finding a person placed by a relative residing in the same or another country. The person placing the Tracing Request provides information about their child, such as if the child was on that boat, a possible location, his characteristics, etc in the framework of a standardized procedure.

Tracing requests are placed by relatives with the assistance of accredited RC members. The Tracing Request form contains data about the person to be traced, persons(s) that accompanying the sought person, intended final destination, details of enquiry: date, place, details of last news and source of information (exact circumstances that led to the loss of contact), contact details of persons able to provide information, where was the sought person last seen, and information on the enquirer.

Additionally, if a separated or unaccompanied child looks for their family, the "Registration form for separated and unaccompanied children" is filled in by the Tracing department experts. It contains information such as: the identity of the child who looks for their family, any siblings or other children accompanying the child, child's current location, the history of separation, protection concerns (girl mother, street child, etc.), the person(s)/relatives the child wishes to locate, information disclosure, etc.

In case there are indications that the sought person might be dead, an Annex is attached to the tracing request. This annex contains the physical description of the sought person. It is called Physical Description Document (PDD). The PDD contains the following data: physical description, distinguishing features, e.g. visible skin marks (scars, tattoos, birthmarks, etc.), visible medical characteristics (injuries, malformation, etc.), dental distinguishing features: (missing front teeth, gold teeth, etc.), what the sought person was wearing (jewellery, watch, etc.), identity documents (identity card, driving license, credit card) the person might have been carrying, details of type of clothes, etc.

The tracing request and the Annex are saved on a specialised software for tracing (FLAnswers).

Another activity of the Tracing Department is "Trace the Face", a tracing program set up by the International Family Links Network consisting by the International Committee of the Red Cross (ICRC) and the Tracing Services of the Red Cross and Red Crescent Societies (in Europe initially) to help mainly people on the move, such as refugees and migrants to find their missing family members. 23 countries in Europe participate in the specific program and currently the program is expanding outside Europe as well. On the website www.tracetheface.org, people who are looking for missing relatives or who lost contact with their loved ones along the migration route, can publish a photo of themselves. Moreover, the photo is on posters hanging on RC offices and in key places all around Europe. By using "Trace the Face", they increase the chance to find their family, who may also look for them. The only information published is the photo and the nature of the family link to the missing relative. All other information, like the name, location, etc. is kept confidential. The Trace the Face Office also involves a back-office application, where information about missing persons and unaccompanied children can be uploaded. Trace the Face back office is secured and only accredited persons from National Red Cross Societies and ICRC have access to it.

3.2.1.2 Coordination and Collaboration

Accommodation of Unaccompanied Minors

Whenever a minor voluntarily departs from a RC's hosting facility or there is a change on the unaccompanied minor's status, e.g. the minor is transported to another hosting facility, then the facility's social service immediately informs the other accommodation centre (if the child is transported there), the police, the public prosecutor, the Ministry of Migration Policy, EKKA, and the RC's HQ.

Additionally, if a person is transported from a hosting facility that RC operates to another organisation's hosting facility, the social service of the RC's facility forwards the minor's file to the new facility.

If a resident of other facility visits a RC's hosting facility (to meet with friends or family), the social service of the facility informs relevant actors, to verify that the person hasn't been registered as missing.

If an unaccompanied minor voluntarily departs from a RC's hosting facility and goes to another's country's hosting facility (RC's or not) and gives the same or a different name than before, there is no centralised method to cross-check the person's previous accommodation.

One day after the voluntary departure of a person, and if he or she is not accounted for, their place in the facility is considered vacant, so EKKA and the Ministry of Migration Policy are informed, and they are able to issue a new placement order for another unaccompanied minor. Of course, if the unaccompanied minor returns to the hosting facility or transported to another facility and requests to return where they were staying, they are able to do so, but only within the one-day time limit, otherwise the process restarts from an earlier stage.

As far as the RC's volunteers, there are three types of volunteers: nursing volunteers, volunteers of social welfare and the volunteer Samaritans corps. The RC's volunteer corps includes more than 12000 active volunteers at any moment and is spread among 86 regional branches all over Greece.

The basic training of Samaritans, which acts also as a Search and Rescue Team lasts 15 months. As far as the cooperation of Samaritans with SoC's volunteers, the two volunteer networks are complementary.

RC also collaborates with METAdrasi. METAdrasi was established in 2014 and is the first structured Network of specially trained Guardians in Greece. The Guardianship Network consists of 70 members who act in close cooperation with the Public Prosecutors for minors and with the First Instance Public Prosecutors in their areas of operation. It supports minors who are detained or staying in accommodation centres and provides them with care specific to their needs⁶.

RC also collaborates with the International Organisation for Migration (IOM), the local medical services in the cities that RC operates its centres and safe zones, plenty of organisations that deal with children, drug rehabilitation centres, UNHCR.

The Tracing Service

A few volunteers are directly engaged in active tracing activities when required, and they are not necessarily members of Search & Rescue teams. They are dispersed in Greece by having at least one or two appointed in every administrative region of the country. Currently, out of the thirteen administrative regions of Greece, only nine are covered, which means that when needed, volunteers from other regions travel to perform these activities.

If the Tracing department decides that a tracing request is a police matter, e.g. when an unaccompanied minor is sought and there are indications that the minor is in imminent danger, the enquirer is suggested to also inform authorities. In such cases humanitarian tracing can also be the case in parallel after the request of the initial enquirer.

If a person being traced might be dead, the Physical Description Document (PDD) is sent to other RC's divisions (both Greece and other countries) and to the forensic team.

If an active investigation is required, especially regarding disasters (shipwrecks, natural disasters, large scale accidents etc.), the search and rescue teams of the Samaritans might be activated, however with the green light of authorities and in cooperation with the Tracing Service.

3.2.1.3 Action Stage

Accommodation of Unaccompanied Minors

The RC doesn't perform active investigations in case of an unaccompanied minor's voluntary departure from its shelters.

⁶ <http://metadrasi.org/en/campaigns/guardianship-of-unaccompanied-minors/>

The Tracing Service

After filling out or receiving the tracing request and if needed coordinate with the authorities, the Tracing Service tries to communicate with the sought person's family members, relatives, acquaintances. If this effort fails and if there are indications that the sought person might be in a specific area in the country, and is deemed necessary, the Samaritans corps can be notified to initiate a search and rescue operation according to a standardized operational procedure with the consent of the RC Governance.

A special case where a form of an active investigation that usually starts with a tracing request can be activated for the specific case of unaccompanied migrant minors under RC's care, is if there is a natural disaster or another other catastrophic event at a location where the minors are accommodated. The list of accommodated minors in a hosting facility can be used as reference document for the Samaritans. RC is currently working on a contingency plan for emergency response where different roles and cooperation in times of emergency would be fully described as standardized. In the meantime, during emergencies all RC activities are coordinated through a task force consisting of the Heads and Coordinators of the different RC Divisions and are validated by the RC Governance (centralized system).

3.2.1.4 Archiving

For the protection service, if the location of an unaccompanied minor, who voluntarily departed from a RC's facility, is not detected within 1 day of their absence, then the RC's social service stops documenting the case. However, the case remains open, until the minor is found. If, however, an unaccompanied minor reaches adulthood while in the care of RC, the person ceases to be under the organisation's care.

For the Tracing Department, a sought person's case is closed when they are traced, or 3 years after the initial tracing request, or when the tracing request is cancelled. Additionally, in case of an unaccompanied minor's disappearance, if the minor reaches a guardian, the case is closed successfully. Communication of the minor with the guardian is enough; then the unaccompanied minor's file is updated, and they are no longer considered missing.

The case files for the tracing requests, as well as the files collected for the unaccompanied minors remain secured in the RC's TS Archives; information extracts and certificates from individual files might be issued after a relative request with the consent of individuals involved and only to serve a humanitarian purpose.

3.2.2 TO-BE scenario

ChildRescue's purpose is not the replacement of the existing processes but their improvement in terms of efficiency and effectiveness, by providing tools that will help with the coordination and the decision making in the organisation. A very important new requirement that was extracted from the interview with the RC was to come up with a solution to the reinforcement of co-ordination mechanisms within the organisation and between the services for the accommodation and protection of unaccompanied minors and tracing. The scenarios that follow take this into account, by enabling a internal mechanism for the sharing of information and a smooth information flow.

3.2.2.1 Preparation and Profiling

Accommodation of Unaccompanied Minors

One problem of the profiling part of the process is the discontinuation of information. For example, the unaccompanied minor is registered many times e.g. when the minor is transported from one hosting facility to another, even managed from the same organisation. Additionally, it is common for a child to go missing and re-emerge in other locations, with the obvious risk of being reregistered multiple times. Today, there is no mechanism of cross-checking that the same unaccompanied minor that voluntarily leaves from a hosting facility and reaches another hosting facility in another country or in some cases in the same one, is the same child. EKKA keeps relevant records of the minors but crosschecking becomes challenging if the minor gives a different name each time, or if his name is spelt differently each time.

To avoid this, ChildRescue will aggregate the unaccompanied minor's available information on the history of the facilities that he stayed in, eliminating overlaps, extending each profile with information that can help with the identification even without providing a name, so that the unaccompanied child will be more easily found and matched. This record will also include information about the locations the minor has been, the routes that he followed or intends to follow, etc. This information will be able to be shared between organisations, which operate hosting facilities of unaccompanied minors and will be accessible only to users in the centre of operations of the organisations.

This solution will reduce the paperwork and will assist in both accommodation and protection, and tracing processes. If a minor is transported to another hosting facility, the record of the minor will be instantly sent to the other facility's social service, by transferring the responsibility of keeping the record to the other facility, instead of copying or physically moving documents. Further to this, if a minor had voluntarily left a facility and a tracing request has been put on him, the tracing service will be able to search the records and immediately retrieve all the relevant information. Consequently, there will be better communication and collaboration between the two services. To achieve this, most of the information collected in the various forms for tracing requests and unaccompanied minors will become part of the profile in the platform.

The way the profiling and preparation is performed also affects the quality and the integrity of the archives. Therefore, the process of profiling is closely related to the process of the archiving and the efficiency of search requests and data analytics on past cases.

Lastly, the platform may be used for holding the list of the currently accommodated minors, allowing the facility manager to directly review the names of the minors when counting them and be able to instantly declare that one of them is missing to the centre of operations. If there are reasons to suspect that his life is in danger, an active investigation could potentially be launched in a matter of minutes.

The Tracing Service

When there is a tracing request to the Tracing Service, the information and the tracing request form, and additional documents, if any, will be uploaded on ChildRescue, to aggregate all the available information about the sought person.

Furthermore, when a tracing request becomes a police matter, the authorities could be provided with all the required information very quickly, either as reports by electronic means or print-outs.

3.2.2.2 Coordination and Collaboration

Accommodation of Unaccompanied Minors

When there is any change of the unaccompanied minor's status (return or not within 1 day of voluntary departure, minor's transport to another facility), the relevant actors could be informed through the platform.

The Tracing Service

Today, the communication with volunteers is mainly done by phone, which restricts the types and the immediacy of information that can be shared. Other communication channels like emails can fill this gap, but their content isn't standardised and so the transfer is inefficient. In contrast, ChildRescue's information sharing can be performed by providing access to all or part of the information contained in a profile to the leader and possibly to members of Search & Rescue or other volunteer teams instantly. At the same time, finding out the availability of the volunteer teams' members can be done for the entire team by broadcasting the request for assistance to all of them at once. If there is an active investigation, the team members will be able to share multimedia files (e.g. photographs) on the fly with the entire team.

For example, if volunteers were to be on a Greek island's beach searching for someone who was on a shipwreck after a tracing request, and there are indications that the person may have reached the shore, and they have only been given a description of the sought person, the organisation could update the profile with pictures or other information, and make it instantly available to all the members of the team or teams looking for him. The information is not scattered into several emails, phone conversations and printed material.

This sharing of information can become a significant tool for cross-border collaboration, in which, if access is provided between different organisations or national branches of the same organisation, identifying minors that have travelled across borders will be as easy as if they travelled between cities in one country.

3.2.2.3 Action Stage

The Tracing Service

The ChildRescue platform could assist in locating minors that have left voluntarily a hosting facility and a tracing request has been made for them or in case of disasters hitting hosting facilities. For example, if an earthquake or a flood damages a hosting facility, the minors evacuate the facility and the organisation needs to run a Search & Rescue operation, the team members could be instantly notified through the platform with all the profiles of the minors that need to be found, together with the search radius to look at. Additionally, alerts could be sent to the ChildRescue simple users and visitors in the area specified for the alert.

3.2.2.4 Archiving

As noted, most of the records kept in every case's record are in paper format. Consequently, the accumulated records over a prolonged period of time require a lot of physical storage space. Searching through them is not efficient. Therefore, a significant goal in archiving is to reduce the paperwork and printed material by creating, metadata annotated, digital content. This will not only allow for faster search and retrieval of past cases, but also for data analysis in uniformly-built historical data. A dashboard with statistics, analytics, and other important information in the passage of time based on the archived records would be a very useful reporting tool and an asset for the organisation.

Finally, when the case is closed, and if there is no reasonable need to keep personally identifiable information about the minors, these will be either anonymised or deleted.

3.2.3 Derived User Requirements

ChildRescue’s target is to provide the RC a new asset that will assist in the existing processes of the Organisation without necessarily altering the way the RC already functions. Immediate and viable information sharing could be crucial in emergencies (e.g. a rescue operation from a sunk boat), while an accessible unified database will accelerate registration processes. After analysing the whole process followed by the RC from the moment an unaccompanied minor comes under the organisation’s responsibility, which is described in the AS-IS scenarios, and comparing it to the TO-BE scenarios, we have traced a number of improvements that are presented here as derived user requirements. This is an initial set of user requirements and after application on pilots and users it will be expanded and further detailed.

In Table 3-2, all the derived user requirements for RC are presented, grouped by the 4 sub-processes, with few belonging to core functionality. The user groups are mapped according to the ChildRescue Platform’s actors as described in Table 4-5 of this deliverable and denote the active side of each requirement.

Table 3-2 Derived User Requirements for the Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minors Use Case

#	Sub-Process	Requirement Description	User group (relevant Actor)
1	Core	Registration to the ChildRescue platform.	All
2	Core	Different access level and privileges for each user group.	All
3	Preparation/ Profiling	Collect all available information about the unaccompanied minor from current and past hosting facilities, avoiding multiple registrations and duplicates.	Organisation Case Manager, Hosting Facility Manager
4	Preparation/ Profiling	Make use of digital content (text data from forms, photos) and social media for minors’ enhanced profiling.	Organisation Case Manager, Hosting Facility Manager
5	Preparation/ Profiling	Improve the data exchange and synergies between departments of RC for a more complete profiling process.	Organisation Case Manager
6	Preparation/ Profiling	Information sharing between the Organisation and hosting facilities. Instant transfer of minor’s record in case of transportation between facilities.	Organisation Case Manager, Hosting Facility Manager
7	Preparation/ Profiling	In case of a tracing request, all relevant Stakeholders should be notified and have access (according to their role) to relevant documents and information through the platform.	Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Network Manager, Volunteer Team Member
8	Collaboration/ Coordination	Improve the communication and information exchange between the RC services, the volunteer corps, the search & rescue teams and the authorities by using a collaboration space	Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Network Manager, Volunteer Team Member

9	Collaboration/ Coordination	Teams can notify their team members for participation in a new investigation operation and check their availability	Organisation Network Manager, Volunteer Team Member
10	Collaboration/ Coordination	Better communication and collaboration among members of the same team and among teams. Real-time guidance by team leaders.	Volunteer Team Member
11	Collaboration/ Coordination	Improve cross-border and international cooperation with other RC national societies, or with other organisations/ NGOs.	Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Network Manager, Organisation Coordinator, Organisation Owner
12	Collaboration/ Coordination	Receive instant notification of emergencies and natural disasters	Volunteer Team Member
13	Collaboration/ Coordination	Receive location-based alerts regarding a natural disaster or emergency and relevant information	Simple user, Volunteer Team Member
14	Action Stage	The volunteers network would be more efficient by having all necessary information available on-the-fly through a mobile application	Volunteer Team Member
15	Action Stage	The search and rescue teams (e.g. Samaritans) would be more efficient if their members could share their position in a real-time map	Volunteer Team Member
16	Archiving	Cases are closed in a privacy-respectful manner and are semantically annotated for easier retrieval. Paperwork and printed material should be reduced.	Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Coordinator
17	Archiving	Unify information and eliminate overlaps among departments by using a common database structure. Necessary for analysing past data and find patterns.	Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Coordinator
18	Archiving	After closure of a case, all sensitive private data will be removed from the platform and public access/users' devices. Only statistics and non-personal data could remain public.	Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Coordinator

4 System Requirements

4.1 Generalised System Requirements

In this section, an analysis of the System Requirements will be performed based on the scenarios and the derived user requirements performed in Sections 3.1 and 3.2. **Error! Reference source not found.** The analysis will take the form of the definition of functional and non-functional requirements which will provide input to *Task 3.1-Components and APIs Design and Platform Architecture*. More specifically, the requirements described in the present deliverable will address the issue of *what* the system should perform; the technical requirements and the architecture which will be defined in *T3.1* will then address the issue of *how* the functionality derived from the functional and non-functional requirements will be achieved.

The specification of both the functional and non-functional requirements will follow the same approach. All requirements will be given a unique identifier. Non-functional requirements will be prefixed by "NFR_" while functional requirements will be prefixed by "FR_" for requirements applicable to both scenarios, "FR_MC_" for requirements applicable to the Missing Children Emergency Use Case and "FR_UM_" for the requirements applicable to the Discovery and Identification Use Case of Unaccompanied Minors.

The phrasing for every requirement will also follow a common schema. Figure 4-1 depicts the sequence of phrases and words used to form a requirement. More specifically,

1. Optionally, define the condition under which this requirement is expected to be fulfilled at first
2. State the name of the "system". ChildRescue will be used exclusively here.
3. Denote whether this requirement is a must-have requirement by using *must*, or a nice-to-have requirement by using *should*.
4. Denote what the system is supposed to do in this requirement. This can be an active process, a process by which the system provides something to other parts of the system/user or a passive process in the sense that the system should be able to react in a specific way under the conditions described.
5. State the object to which the actions performed by the system apply to.
6. Denote any additional details about the object that may be needed.

Figure 4-1: Requirement Specification

For the purposes of the system requirement analysis when a requirement refers to a “user”, this will be done in the general user of platform. In case the requirement refers specifically to an operator (a user typically belonging to the organisation staff group, see also Section 3.1.3) this user will be denoted as “operational user”. Users of the mobile application (typically belonging to the volunteers user group, see also Section 3.1.3 **Error! Reference source not found.**, or citizens) will be referred as “mobile users”. “Volunteer” or “citizen” will be used if a requirement relevant to a mobile user refers exclusively to a member of the respective sub-group.

The next two sections perform the above exercise for all the identified requirements

4.1.1 Functional Requirements

Functional requirements refer to specific behavior and functionality that the ChildRescue platform should have. As noted in Section 4.1 three groups of functional requirements are considered, the ones that are common on all use cases, the ones specific to the Missing Children Emergency Use Case and the ones specific to the Discovery and Identification Use Case of Unaccompanied Minors. The set of functional requirements documented in the present deliverable, is derived from the TO-BE scenarios and reflects, broadly, the set of features that are identified from the stakeholder’s requests. As the Methodology of ChildRescue is developed, every functional requirement documented here will be expanded to functional requirements derived for each use case; this process is taking place under *T3.1-Components and APIs Design and Platform Architecture*.

In general, ChildRescue must provide mechanisms for exchanging information between headquarter departments as well as between registered volunteers and headquarter. The option to store data in fragmented way and to anonymise them before storing or transmitting should always be available to users. Alerts should be able to be generated automatically in case of a significant status update and public social media content should be monitored in case significant information is posted.

For the Missing Children Emergency Use Case, volunteers should be notified according to their location, so the mobile application of ChildRescue should be location-aware. Fragmentation of data is a challenge in the case of RC, that ChildRescue, so data normalisation and alignment between the various departments is also a necessary requirement.

Table 4-1 summarises the list of general functional requirements while Table 4-2 and Table 4-3 summarise the functional requirements for the cases of Missing Children Emergency Use Case and the Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minors Use Case respectively.

Table 4-1 General Functional Requirements

Requirement	Description
FR_1	ChildRescue must provide operational users the ability to dispatch information to field teams
FR_2	ChildRescue must provide operational users the ability to dispatch information to volunteer users
FR_3	ChildRescue must provide operational users the ability to dispatch information between departments
FR_4	ChildRescue must allow users to store data fragmented

FR_5	ChildRescue must allow users to anonymise data
FR_6	ChildRescue must be operational users to give push notifications to mobile users
FR_7	ChildRescue must be able to monitor public social media accounts.
FR_8	ChildRescue must notify operational users when new post is made in monitored accounts.
FR_9	ChildRescue must provide to users that want to register documents that need to be signed
FR_10	ChildRescue must require users to sign digitally the registration documents.
FR_11	ChildRescue must provide a user with the ability to register with a pseudonym

Table 4-2 Functional Requirements for the Missing Children Emergency Use Case

Requirement	Description
FR_MC_1	When the functionality is enabled, ChildRescue must provide users of the mobile application location-based alerts
FR_MC_2	ChildRescue must be able to correlate the location of mobile users with the area of incident.
FR_MC_3	ChildRescue should be able to provide operational users suggestions for next steps
FR_MC_4	ChildRescue must allow authorised users to update the file of any case
FR_MC_5	ChildRescue should provide the operators with alerts when a monitored social media account provides input relevant to a case.
FR_MC_6	ChildRescue should provide the users with suggestions based on analysis of past profiles and past cases
FR_MC_7	ChildRescue should provide the users with suggestions based on analysis of monitored social media accounts posts.

Table 4-3 Functional Requirements for the Discovery and Identification Use Case of Unaccompanied Minors

Requirement	Description
FR_UM_1	ChildRescue must provide the users the means to digitise any past archived forms
FR_UM_2	ChildRescue must provide the users the means to store centrally information needed by the various departments

FR_UM_3	ChildRescue must allow users from different teams and departments to exchange information
FR_UM_4	ChildRescue must be able to generate event reports for natural disasters
FR_UM_5	ChildRescue must be able to normalise data by merging duplicate information and categorising existing entries.
FR_UM_6	ChildRescue should provide the ability to perform database checks through voice recognition
FR_UM_7	ChildRescue must be able to analyse profiles
FR_UM_8	ChildRescue should be able to generate alerts based on the results of the profile analysis.

4.1.2 Non-functional Requirements

Non-functional requirements refer to the general operation of the system rather than specific behavior or functionality. In general, since all agencies work 24/7, the system is expected to have no downtime. Personal data must under no circumstance be exposed, while significant data need to be archived and, if needed, recovered. Generally, response times may not need to be rapid, since the critical processes for finding a child or a parent take place on the field; however, they must be acceptable by the end users (both operators and participating citizens) and should be the lowest possible. The issue of transparency is also significant. If a user has doubts about the validity of the matching or the privacy algorithms being implemented, she/he must have proper access to the documentation.

Table 4-4 lists all the non-functional requirements expected to be fulfilled by ChildRescue.

Table 4-4 Non-functional Requirements

Requirement	Description
NFR_1	ChildRescue must have mean time between failures equal to zero
NFR_2	When a sub-system fails, ChildRescue must fall back to a secondary sub-system immediately
NFR_3	ChildRescue must provide a user with the ability to register with credentials
NFR_4	ChildRescue must be able to protect any personal data stored
NFR_5	ChildRescue must be able to encrypt any data transmitted
NFR_6	ChildRescue should provide the user with the ability to operate it in any platform
NFR_7	ChildRescue must be able to archive any significant data required by the user
NFR_8	In the case of destruction, ChildRescue must be able to recover all significant data

NFR_9	ChildRescue must have acceptable response times
NFR_10	ChildRescue should have low response times
NFR_11	ChildRescue must provide transparency to any algorithms executed.
NFR_12	ChildRescue must provide role support with different authorisation levels

4.2 1st iteration of User Stories

In agile terminology, a User Story is a short, generally one-sentence, description of a functionality available and valuable to the user of a system from the user’s perspective. A large user story that can be split into two or more stories of smaller is commonly referred to as an Epic Story or just Epic [1], and it is often used to group stories that have the same purpose or objective.

User stories is an invaluable tool, especially in software development. Their ability to convey self-explanatory and time-related information, that is comprehensible by both the user (customer) and the developers, help the latter to produce a reasonable estimation of the effort required to implement it. In consequence, this leads to time saving, more efficient working processes and, ultimately, to better software.

Typically, user stories are proved in the following manner:

As an <actor>, I want <action (to do a thing)> so that <reason>.

This, well-expressed, statement helps to clarify the rationale behind a user requirement and define a required functionality in high level without much detail. In addition, it takes into account the user desires, goals and business value of each requirement.

User stories are recorded in a “user story sheet”, often divided by actor, that includes the following information:

- ID: an arbitrary ID composed by the actor’s name (2-letter) and a number;
- Epic: representing a set of user stories, trying to provide a broader context regarding a specific goal of an actor.
- User Story: A textual description, truncated in the following pieces:
 - *As an <actor role>*: indicating the role of the subject of the story (e.g. the actor identified above) (selection from actor’s list)
 - *I want <action (to do something)>*: the functionality to be added to the solution (free text). This is the core concept of a requirement.
 - *so that <reason>*: the added value of the development suggested (free text)

In an agile project, new or updated user stories are surfacing at any time of implementation, changing the backlog. Such a behaviour is of course desired, as it helps teams to constantly focus on things that matter to users and exclude other features that might not be that important as the value they eventually deliver to both the system and the environment surrounding it.

In this section we perform the 1st iteration of user stories as derived from user requirements in sections 3.1.3 and 3.2.3.

ACTORS

The ChildRescue platform is expected to have the following actors during the missing child investigation process for all use cases:

Table 4-5 ChildRescue Platform's Actors

Actor	Description
Visitor (Anonymous user)	A user that lands on the ChildRescue platform page or downloads the mobile app without logging in. This user is allowed to have a limited interaction with the platform.
Simple User (Registered user)	A registered user that has access to platform features of the coordination and action phase of the investigation. <i>Naturally, this user inherits all privileges (user stories as well) of the "Visitor" user.</i>
Search & Rescue Team Member	A registered and authenticated user that has access to features of the coordination and action phases of the investigation (usually in the field). All members of a Search & Rescue Team have years of expert training and have special skills and equipment that offer to the investigation cause. <i>Inherits all privileges of the "Simple User".</i>
Volunteer Team Member	A volunteer is a registered and authenticated user that has access to features available to the coordination and action phase of the investigation. In contrast to the Search and Rescue Teams, Volunteer candidates do not usually carry some special skill and follow a shorter and more generic educational training. They are approved off-line by the Organisation. <i>Inherits all privileges of the "Simple User".</i>
Hosting Facility Manager	A registered and authenticated user, usually a social worker, that is in charge of an accommodation centre of the Organisation. <i>Inherits all privileges of the "Simple User".</i>
Organisation Case Manager	A registered and authenticated user, usually a social worker, that can feed the system with profiling data and information during the whole process of investigation for a specific case. <i>Inherits all privileges of the "Simple User".</i>
Organisation Network Manager	A registered and authenticated user that is responsible for the network management, i.e. The human resources outside the Organisation, for a specific case. <i>Inherits all privileges of the "Simple User".</i>
Organisation Coordinator Manager	A registered and authenticated user that can initiate and coordinate the whole process of investigation and archive a case

	when it is closed. <i>Inherits all privileges of the "Organisation Case Manager" and the "Organisation Network Manager".</i>
Organisation Owner	A registered and authenticated user that can setup an Organisation and manage its users and roles. Has an overview of all phases for all cases, past and present. <i>Inherits all privileges of the "Organisation Coordinator Manager".</i>
Special Actors	
Organisation	Organisation is an Actor but not a user per se. It is the only "user" the simple users can see and contact. It can be considered an Alias for the Organisation Owner.
Missing child	This is a special case of an actor since this person is the target of the investigation mission. He or she may contact the platform to ask for help.
Parent/Guardian/Relative of the missing child	The actual cause of the initiation of the investigation mission. They may be granted special access by an Organisation in order to passively follow the progress -only- of their case (view news & announcements).

The complete tables of each actor's user stories are presented in Annex III: User Stories By Actor (note: special actors are excluded from this iteration).

Along the following lines and taking as input the ChildRescue user stories describing how ChildRescue is going to contribute to a missing child's investigation process (see Annex III: User Stories By Actor), two use case scenarios were outlined, one for each of the two ChildRescue Use Cases, presented in sections 3.1 and 3.2 of the present deliverable, using the platform's actors, as these were identified above.

4.2.1 USE CASE SCENARIO 1: Missing Children Emergency

This scenario involves the standard case when a child goes missing from his home, his parents report the incident, an amber alert is raised, the community and search parties become engaged, and the child is located and returned to his family. The procedure follows the processes as described in the Stakeholder's Requirements and the Derived System Requirements sections of this document, emphasising the contribution of the ChildRescue parallel processes along the way. As many of the details that refer to profiling methods, algorithms, and other specific technical requirements are to be developed at a later stage of the project, the scenario will treat these specific functionalities as black boxes. Processes or events that are outside of the immediate interest of ChildRescue as an enhancement of already existing operations are either omitted or only briefly mentioned. Those that refer to the User Stories from this document also include their corresponding Epic's User Story code.

The actors involved in this scenario are the following:

Missing Child, Parent/Guardian/Relative of the missing child, Visitor, Simple User, Search & Rescue Team Member, Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Network Manager, Organisation Coordinator Manager

The Scenario:

A parent contacts the Organisation Case Manager (call operator), conveying, by phone, that a missing child report has been made to the police. The Case Manager verifies this with the police. The Organisation Case Manager creates a Case file in ChildRescue (CM.01), asks for and enters the basic information in the case. The Case Manager requests and receives from the parent and/or the police other relevant information, such as pictures, location last seen, social media accounts etc. that get entered in ChildRescue (CM.02, CM.03, CM.04). An Amber Alert is requested to be created and is issued (CM.11, CM.13). An evaluation of the profile and the case is added to the platform (CM.05) and a proposal for the possible location to look at leads to the creation of localised notifications for the mobile application Visitors and Simple Users, including some extended areas along public transportation routes (CM.12, CM.14).

A Simple User about ten kilometres away from the area that the child went missing has already registered with the platform via the mobile application eponymously and has enabled location services (SU.01, SU.02, SU.03). While driving his car near a forest area, he sees a child that seems disoriented by the edge of the road. After a few minutes and wondering what he should do, he visits the mobile application and filters the list of missing children using his location, the date of disappearance and what he believes to be the age of the child he saw (SU.07, SU.08, SU.09). He sees a child that might look like the one he saw on the street and sees that it went missing ten kilometres away from him. He believes that the child couldn't have gotten so far by foot, so he just shares the alert on his social media account (SU.10). He then receives the localised notification (SU.15), that the child he thought to have seen might be near him, based on the possible public transportation routes and their range. He opens the Missing Child Card in the application and selects to notify the organisation looking for him, selecting on the map where he believes he saw the child (SU.12).

The Case Manager sees the message sent while monitoring the investigation, along with other messages that ended up being false flags (CM.15, CM.16, CM.17, CM.18). He replies to the message asking for more details, along with a phone number to call, which the Simple User receives (SU.14). After providing a few more details via the application, he calls to the given number and the Case Manager adds the witness report to the platform (CM.02, CM.05). The Case Manager asks for assistance from the Organisation Coordinator (CM.10).

The Organisation Coordinator receives the request from the Case Manager (OC.02) and opens the list of active cases and the map (OC.06, OC.07). Looking at the specific case (OC.01), he considers the witness report to be credible and assigns a Network Manager to perform a Search & Rescue Operation giving him information on the case and a location to search (OC.01, OC.02, OC.05, OC.09).

The Network Manager receives his assignment and the information regarding the case (NM.01, NM.05). He initiates an active Search & Rescue operation by notifying the appropriate team (NM.02). While the operation is active, he is monitoring and coordinating the communications of the search party and sending more information in the form of messages and additional pictures of the child (NM.03) by locating them on the map, widening the search area as time passes (NM.06, NM.07, NM.08).

A Search & Rescue team leader is notified, and a team member receives a notification that his team was requested to search for the missing child in an area pinpointed on the map, together with the location where the team will gather up and additional pictures (RT.02, RT.04). He messages the rest of the team members that he is available (RT.03), he prepares himself and goes to that location. When reaching the location where the search is going to start, he receives updated information on the case

with the new radius and locations to look at (RT.05). The team coordinates with the police where everyone is going to be headed and starts to look for the child. He starts looking for the child and after a while he sees a child sitting under a tree exhausted. Speaking calmly to the child, he takes a geo-tagged picture of the child and sends it to the group discussion, mentioning that he found a child who seems to be the one they were looking for (RT.04).

The Network Manager receives the latest information and updates the Coordinator and the Case Manager that the child may have been found, providing the picture and the location on the map (NM.04, NM.09). The Case Manager contacts the police in case the Search & Rescue Team member hasn't already with the location of the sighting. The police reach the point, pick up the child, and the Network Manager notifies the team that the search is over, and the child was found (NM.03). The team evacuates the area.

After validation by the police that the child was identified as the one missing, the Case Manager closes and archives the case (CM.06). The Coordinator writes up a brief report on the case and its results and files it in ChildRescue (OC.10).

4.2.2 USE CASE SCENARIO 2: Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minor and natural disaster

This scenario dives deeper into the case where a child isn't missing, but has the status of an unaccompanied minor, who is in the care of the organisation in a hosting facility it operates. In this scenario actions regarding profiling, coordination and communication mostly refer to those that are done pre-emptively in case the minor goes missing. This is done to cover for the lack of communication with a parent or close relative that could have provided extensive profiling information if requested. The scenario involves a minor who enters a facility and then leaves for another facility along the expected trail towards his final destination in another country to find relatives. If the minor goes missing from the facility in circumstances that might warrant the issuing of an Amber Alert or another kind of active investigation, the provisions of Use Case Scenario 1 apply, with the additional conditions that the police might not be involved and that the status of the legal guardian may be given to either the Hosting Facility Manager or a prosecutor. Instead of running this part of the scenario in this case, we are considering the possibility that a natural disaster occurs in the second facility and the active investigation has to do with multiple minors residing there. Like the Use Case Scenario 1, the focus is on the activities ran only by the organisation, are related to the ChildRescue platform, and the corresponding Epic's User Story code is mentioned. Additionally, parts of the activities in the active investigation are omitted, as they are already described in the Use Case Scenario 1.

The actors involved in this scenario are the following:

(potential) Missing Child, Hosting Facility Manager, Visitor, Simple User, Search & Rescue Team Member, Organisation Case Manager, Organisation Network Manager, Organisation Coordinator Manager

The Scenario:

An unaccompanied migrant minor who is appointed to stay at a Hosting Facility meets the Hosting Facility Manager. The Hosting Facility Manager interviews the minor and asks a series of questions while he searches in ChildRescue using that information for a match (FM.03). He doesn't find one, so he creates a new profile and starts to fill it in with information coming from the documents given and the answers the minor gives (FM.02). He then proceeds to upload the documents to the profile and edit

them accordingly (FM.04, FM.05). One piece of information given by the minor is that his final destination is in another country. A month later, while counting the minors in the morning, the Hosting Facility Manager notices that the minor left during the night. Asking the other residents what happened, he concludes that the minor has resumed traveling towards his destination but might visit a cousin who resides in another hosting facility. He notifies an Organisation's Case Manager about the fact and sends some additional information (FM.06, FM.08, CM.01) and a notification is sent to hosting facilities where friends or relatives reside (FM.08). The Case Manager requests assistance from the Organisation Coordinator and sends him the relevant profile and his assertion (CM.19) that an active investigation isn't warranted (CM.10, CM.20). The Coordinator concurs, closes the case (OC.01) and files in a brief report (OC.10).

A few weeks later the minor reappears in a Hosting Facility in another country along the route towards his destination with fresh paperwork. The Hosting Facility Manager interviews the minor and asks a series of questions while he searches in ChildRescue using that information for a match (FM.3). The minor says that he is travelling from his home country towards a city in the current country where he has family. When asked about residing in other Hosting Facilities in the past, he says that he doesn't remember the names of the places he has been but says that it was an island in the country he was before. As the minor has a very common name, along other information, the Hosting Facility Manager searches the platform by focusing on the geographic area created by the crude estimation of the places the minor has been and the routes towards his current location. He finds a match and updates the profile with the new assignment to the facility and the documents provided (FM.02, FM.04, FM.05). He consults the previous Hosting Facility Manager if there were any special issues and concerns that haven't been entered in the profile about the minor (FM.10) and gets a negative reply.

A few weeks later a natural disaster hits the second facility. The residents are evacuated hastily, the buildings are damaged, but the circumstances don't allow the minors and the workers of the facility to meet somewhere. The Hosting Facility Manager finds a few minors and reports the rest of them as potentially missing to a Case Manager (FM.06, FM.09, FM.01). He also uploads additional information about the cases (FM.08) The Case Manager, in collaboration with the Coordinator and Network Manager organise a Search & Rescue mission and inform the Hosting Facility Manager about it (FM.10). The Search & Rescue Team leader and the members are notified by the Network Manager, they meet on location and start their search. Whenever a minor is found, the Hosting Facility Manager is notified (FM.10) and the minor is transferred to the temporary accommodation that was set up. After all minors have been accounted for, the missing cases close and are returned to their previous status (OC.01) by the Coordinator, who also files in a report (OC.10) on the events.

5 Conclusions

As in any project that aims to combine the expertise of heterogeneous parties, ChildRescue needs to create a mutual understanding of the particularities of what and who is involved when designing, implementing, and running new processes and new software systems. In this case, bringing together the technical partners of the project with the NGOs and sociologists, and engaging in long, structured, and meaningful conversations through the interview process and the questionnaires was enlightening. Most aspects of the initial proposal for the project have matured significantly as a result. The Smile of the Child, the Hellenic Red Cross and Child Focus have provided extensive information about the processes that they run for many years now, which in turn has allowed the identification and the extraction of all those relevant to ChildRescue. At the same time, when there was no clear answer as to how the two different pilot cases could be merged under the same methodology and platform before, now this merging appears to be obvious and intuitive. The systematic identification of these processes and the input from the NGO partners has led to the creation of the first set of user requirements, the generalised system requirements, the user stories, and the use case scenarios in this document and prepared the ground for the definition of the project's methodology that ensues.

Some of the key conclusions drawn from the implementation of this task, and which are different from what was initially expected are:

- Public Authorities, like the police, fire departments, public prosecutors, although very important stakeholders to the project, will not be included as system users. Several flags have been raised, including the need for protection from prosecution of minors, the significant difficulty to make public bodies adopt innovative technologies and processes, and the need, in most cases, to have novel solutions first passed as legislation. As ChildRescue employs a bottom-up approach, even if privacy wasn't a concern, an effort to introduce the project to public institutions would take probably longer than the project's duration and would have uncertain benefits.
- Every organisation will have its own set of data and operational control. Steering away from the initial idea to have a common searchable database on a platform level for all authorised organisational users, ChildRescue will be implemented on a common software platform, but with independent datasets and functions between different organisations. By doing this, the question of which organisation will be responsible for performing an action on a shared case will never need to be asked, while at the same time there is clear ownership of the data. Sharing of data between organisations will happen only on specific cases when one organisation either requires assistance from another, or when it transfers the case's ownership.
- Users from the general public, either visitors or simple users, will not be allowed any kind of access to profiles of children, especially for unaccompanied minors, if a missing child alert hasn't been raised by the police. Furthermore, access to these data will not be even organisation-wide, but only available to the Hosting Facility Manager actors and their superiors. Actors on the same level (i.e. volunteers) will only gain access to these data on a case by case basis, only when their contribution is required.
- Each organisation will have actors and roles assigned for their independent centre of operations, where all decision making is made. This centre of operations is conceptual and not

necessarily based on the same physical premises but will offer hierarchical operational control similar and parallel to the current processes.

- Feedback and communication from visitors and simple users will have only a single direction: up. There will be no support for public user profiles, and no means for communication given by the platform between users belonging to the general public. The information disseminated about specific cases to the general public will contain no more information than the public missing children alerts already in place, to ensure that ChildRescue will never become a tool for witch-hunting and mob justice.
- Due to the sensitivity of the matter at hand, and following the Decision Support Systems paradigm, ChildRescue will make no decisions of its own in an automatic manner. The platform will make predictions and suggestions in the form of consultancy, but any decision on them must be made by a human with sufficient qualifications and authority. For example, when issuing a location-based alert, the platform will suggest some areas to send it, but the user will be able to modify them, add more, delete some, or even ignore them altogether.

Overall, the work done, and the results of this task have managed to set a clear shared course for the methodology and the platform, towards creating and providing tools that will be primarily useful to the pilot partners and consequently to any other similar organisations that will join ChildRescue in the future.

Annex I: References

- [1] Cohn, M. (2004). User Stories Applied: For Agile Software Development. Addison-Wesley Professional.

Annex II: Questionnaires

Questionnaire about SOC's/CF's process

Below lies the questionnaire about SOC's process. The CF's questionnaire is the same as SOC's, where instead of SOC there is CF.

1. Preparation
 - What are the main steps of the SoC's Missing Children Investigation Process (MCIP)?
 - Who are the main actors of SoC that are engaged in the MCIP? What is their role?
 - Do you receive a call by the police, in case they are firstly informed about a child disappearance?
 - Do you inform the police in case you are firstly informed about a child disappearance? Who informs the police?
 - If you receive a call about a missing child, who is in charge to identify the caller's request?
 - What happens after the identification of the caller's request?
 - Who is the call operator?
 - What sort of information they gather?
 - Who and how do you gather the information?
 - Do you use phone or do you also go directly at the child's house for collecting information from the parents and the friends of the child?
 - Where and in which format do you store the information you get (hand written, word, database)?
 - Are you able to verify this information?
 - How long does it take to gather this information?
 - Is this the input of the process?
 - What are the risks that missing children face?
 - What happens next?

2. Coordination
 - Is someone appointed case manager? What is their role?
 - Who is responsible for finding a missing child?
 - Who is being appointed case manager?
 - What happens next?
 - Which are the additional sources, from which you gather information?
 - Do you share with the appropriate official authorities the information that you gather?
 - Do these authorities share with you, the information they have?
 - Do you collaborate with other organisations that are engaged in missing children investigation process? Which are these organisations? How do you cooperate with them? What sort of information do you share with them?
 - What happens next?

3. Action
 - What is the first step of communicating the child's disappearance?
 - Are there other bodies and partner organisations to be notified, e.g. search and rescue/volunteer teams?
 - Who notifies them?

- Why are these organisations selected?
- What sort of information do you share with them?
- Do you have a Uniform Data Base? Do all SoC's facilities have access to a common database?
- Do you apply any profiling methods of the missing child? If yes, what is the basis for profiling (theoretical concept; data analysis? What kind of means are used?
- Are there any experts that work with the family, collecting additional data in order to build an initial psychosocial profile of the missing child?
- Do you also go directly at the missing child's house for collecting information from the parents and the friends of the child?
- Do you provide psychological support to the family?
- Do you need the written consent of the guardian(s) or the legal representative(s) in order to create posters and flyers?
- When does the creation of posters and flyers take place?
- What sort of information do they include?
- Who decides this kind of information?
- Is the written consent of the family needed?
- How and from whom are they distributed?
- How long does it take to print and distribute the flyers?
- What is the duration of this action?
- Which is your geographical reach?
- Do you have any subscribers or volunteers?
- Do you notify them? If yes, when and how do you notify them?
- Do you need the written consent of the family?
- What sort of information is being sent to them? How can somebody become a subscriber? Do they receive some special training?
- Is there cooperation between SoC's volunteers?
- What other systems do you use in order to communicate missing children cases?
- Is there additional equipment that you use in order to find missing children?
- What kind of technology tools do you use?
- What happens if you receive a reliable testimony?
- Do you operate a Hotline e.g. the European Hotline for Missing Children 116000? If yes, on what basis e.g. on a 24/7 basis? Who operates the hotline?
- Do you use social media? Which social media do you use? Who is the manager of the social media accounts? In what way do you use social media?
- What is AMBER/CHILD ALERT system?
- When AMBER ALERT system is being activated? What conditions must be in place for a missing child in order to activate AMBER ALERT?
- How long does it take to be activated?
- What is its duration?
- Is AMBER ALERT system, the last resort in order to find the missing child?
- What happens when the location of the missing child is detected? Who does collect the missing child? What happens when the location of the missing child is not detected?
- What happens if the missing child keeps missing?

4. Archiving
 - When a missing child case is considered closed?
 - What is being done after a case is closed?
 - When does SoC stop trying to trace a missing child?
 - Are there any other questions you think I should be asking, or anything else you want to tell me?
 - Do you have any control points and measurements in the process that you follow?
 - In which steps, could ChildRescue help in order to reduce the existing process's duration?
 - What problems do you encounter with the current process?
 - Which areas of this process can be improved?
 - How ChildRescue will help you to improve your MCIP?

Questionnaire about RC's process

Below lies the questionnaire about RC's process.

1. Profiling
 - What are the steps of the RC's Discovery and Identification of Unaccompanied Minors Process (DIUMP)?
 - Who are the main actors of RC that are engaged in the DIUMP? What is their role?
 - Which children are considered unaccompanied minors?
 - In what way do you provide safety to the unaccompanied minors?
 - Where and when are the unaccompanied minors located for the first time?
 - At which point and by whom are the unaccompanied minors registered?
 - Do you inform the police in case you discover and identify an unaccompanied minor?
 - When and how do the unaccompanied minors come to RC's UMC centres or other RC's hosting facilities?
 - What information do you get from them, e.g. photograph, age, name, surname, height, weight, country, location of their parents, relatives, where they want to go? Where and in which format do you store the information you get from them (hand written, word, database)? Are you able to verify this information?
 - Where do the unaccompanied minors stay?
 - How many UMC centres does RC operate in Greece? Where are they? How many unaccompanied minors are hosted in the UMC centres?
 - Does RC operate reception centres? What responsibilities does RC have at a reception centre? What documents do you collect from the unaccompanied minors?
 - Who is responsible for the unaccompanied minors?
 - Who else could be responsible for them?
 - What is the role of the Public Prosecutor?
 - When does a child come to the attention of RC; When is there a reason to believe that the child may present a "high-risk" of disappearance?
 - What are the indications that some unaccompanied minors are at greater risk of disappearance than others, e.g. if they have relatives in other cities?
 - Do you consider that some special characteristics of unaccompanied minors (e.g. a girl or a boy under the age of 12) place some children at greater risk than others?

- Do you take any action in this case?
 - What are the risks that unaccompanied minors face?
 - When and how the unaccompanied minors may leave from a reception or a UMC centre?
2. Coordination
- Do you collaborate with other organisations that provide safety to unaccompanied minors? Which are these organisations? Do they operate UMC centres? How do you cooperate with them?
 - Who is responsible for finding an unaccompanied minor who leaves a RC's UMC centre?
 - Who is responsible for finding a disappeared unaccompanied minor?
 - Is someone appointed case manager? What is their role?
3. Action
- How do you find out that an unaccompanied minor leaves a RC's UMC centre? How long does it take to find this out?
 - Do you inform the police in case an unaccompanied minor leaves a RC's UMC centre?
 - Do you cooperate with other bodies and partner organisations, e.g. search and rescue/volunteer teams in case an unaccompanied minor leaves a RC's UMC centre?
 - Who notifies them?
 - Why are these organisations selected?
 - What sort of information do you share with them?
 - What do you do in case you notice an unaccompanied minor leaves a RC's UMC centre?
 - Do you apply any profiling methods of the unaccompanied minors? If yes, what is the basis for profiling (theoretical concept; data analysis)?
 - What is the PDD (physical description form)? What sort of information does the PDD contain? Who does fill in the PDD?
 - Where is the PDD sent?
 - Who does the comparison between the PDD and the physical description?
 - Do you have a Uniform Data Base? Do all RC's shelters have access to a common database?
 - What conditions must be in place for an unaccompanied minor's absence to be regarded as disappearance?
 - What do you do in case you notice an unaccompanied minor's disappearance?
 - Do you inform the police in case you notice an unaccompanied minor's disappearance?
 - Do you inform the Public Prosecutor?
 - Who informs the police?
 - Do you cooperate with other bodies and partner organisations, e.g. search and rescue/volunteer teams in case of an unaccompanied minor's disappearance?
 - Who notifies them?
 - Why are these organisations selected?
 - What sort of information do you share with them?
 - Do you share with other organisations the name, photo and location of unaccompanied minors who stay at your shelters?
 - Which are the conditions to be fulfilled in order to initiate a humanitarian tracing procedure?
 - Who initiates a humanitarian tracing procedure if preconditions are fulfilled?

- What happens next?
 - What is the first step of communicating the unaccompanied minor's disappearance? Do you create any posters or flyers? When does the creation of posters and flyers take place? What sort of information do they include? How and from whom are they distributed? How long does it take?
 - What other systems do you use in order to communicate an unaccompanied minor's disappearance?
 - Is there additional equipment that you use in order to locate disappeared unaccompanied minors?
 - What kind of technology tools do you use?
 - What happens if you receive a reliable testimony?
 - Which are the additional sources, from which you gather information?
 - Do you share with the appropriate official authorities the information that you gather?
 - Do these authorities share with you, the information they have?
 - Which is your geographical reach? Do you have any registered subscribers or volunteers?
 - Do you notify them?
 - If yes, when and how do you notify them?
 - What sort of information is being sent to subscribers?
 - How can somebody become a subscriber?
 - Is there cooperation between RC's volunteers, in order to find out if an unaccompanied minor was at one UMC (or not) shelter and then re-emerged at another UMC (or not) shelter? Is this cooperation transnational?
 - Is there a mechanism of cross-checking that the same unaccompanied minor that gone missing, left from one shelter and went to another, declaring different name than the one it gave to the previous shelter, is the same?
 - Do you operate a Hotline? If yes, on what basis e.g. on a 24/7 basis?
 - Do you use social media? Which social media do you use? Who is the manager of the social media accounts? In what way do you use social media?
 - What happens when the location of the missing unaccompanied minor is detected? Who does collect the missing unaccompanied minor?
 - What happens when the location of the missing unaccompanied minor is not detected?
4. Archiving
- When a missing child case is considered closed? What is being done after a case is closed?
 - When does RC stop trying to trace an unaccompanied minor who leaves from its facilities?
 - Are there any other questions you think I should be asking, or anything else you want to tell me?
 - Which areas of this process can be improved?
 - What problems do you encounter with the current process?
 - How ChildRescue will help you to improve your DIUMP?

Annex III: User Stories By Actor

III.1 User Stories for Actor "Visitor"

As "Visitor" is considered every user of the system that is not registered or not logged on in the platform. This user may contact an Organisation to offer pieces of information anonymously.

#	EPIC	ROLE	GOAL/DESIRE I want...	USER STORY	BENEFIT , so that...
VU.01	Registration	Visitor	to be able to register using minimal details or by using social media accounts	I can be part of the ChildRescue platform.	
VU.02	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to view a list of currently active missing children cases	I can actively participate in the investigation.	
VU.03	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to sort the list of missing children based on their disappearance date	I can see the most recent ones.	
VU.04	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to visit the page of a single case	I can view more details concerning the case.	
VU.05	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to view a list of the participating Organisations and their contact details	I can communicate with Organisations by other means, such as telephone or postal services.	
VU.06	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to view information about the platform, terms of service and usage, etc	I can be fully aware of what the platform is about and what requirements it involves.	
VU.07	Platform Browsing	Visitor	to be able to view information about DOs and DON'Ts regarding missing children investigation.	I can assist the investigation in an appropriate and correct - for the child at risk - manner.	
VU.08	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Visitor	to send feedback in the form of text, image or video the Organisation concerning a missing child by filling-in an appropriate form	I can assist in the investigation mission anonymously.	

III.2 User Stories for Actor “Simple User”

The Simple User is considered to be a registered, logged on user that have access to the Platform, mostly, via a mobile application, and his or her communication is directly with the Organisation and not with other users.

#	EPIC	USER STORY		
		ROLE	GOAL/DESIRE I want...	BENEFIT , so that...
SU.01	Registration	Simple User	to be able to specify some basic, optional personal profile information during the initial registration process	I can have a more complete and reliable personal profile which increases my integrity thus making me a trusted collaborator.
SU.02	Profile Editing	Simple User	to be able to edit my personal profile information	I can have a more complete personal profile which increases my integrity and reliability.
SU.03	Profile Editing	Simple User	to be able to allow geolocation services	I can be contacted based on my current location.
SU.04	Profile Editing	Simple User	to be able to permanently remove my account credentials from the system	I can no longer log-in and not be contacted by other users.
SU.05	Profile Editing	Simple User	to be able to make my profile "private" or hide my details,	I can safekeep my anonymity in respect to my peers.
SU.06	Profile Editing	Simple User	to be able to apply for volunteer for a selected Organisation	I can offer my services in a more official and permanent way and get more privileges in the platform.
SU.07	Platform Browsing	Simple User	to view a list of currently missing children, last seen around my -current- location	I can actively search for them.
SU.08	Platform Browsing	Simple User	to sort the list of missing children based on their disappearance date	I can see the most recent ones.
SU.09	Platform Browsing	Simple User	to filter out cases based on physical characteristics, such as age, hair colour, clothing	I can focus on the right case, in situations where I have a clear live view of a child.
SU.10	Platform Browsing	Simple User	to be able to share information about a case on my social media accounts	I further disseminate information about the case to a larger audience.
SU.11	Platform Browsing	Simple User	to be able to view a list of the participating Organisations and their contact details	I can establish a communication channel with an Organisation directly through the platform.
SU.12	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to send feedback in the form of text, image or video to the Organisation concerning a missing child without the need to fill-in a long form	I can assist in the investigation mission in a quick and efficient manner.
SU.13	Investigation Coordination/	Simple User	to get notified when I have a direct message received	I know a response to my message was provided.

	Communication			
SU.14	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to be able to view messages sent to me and reply	I can continue communication with an Organisation/ Team.
SU.15	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to get notified when there is a missing child case in my vicinity	I can act on it and help the investigation.
SU.16	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to get notified when announcements are made concerning a case in my vicinity	I can be informed with latest news regarding the case.
SU.17	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Simple User	to get notified when a case is closed	I can stop any actions I have taken.
SU.18	Investigation Crowd-sourcing Action	Simple User	to evaluate a piece of information, if requested	I can validate if it is true or false according to my knowledge.

III.3 User Stories for Actor “Search & Rescue Team member”

This actor’s members are considered to be registered and authenticated, logged on users that have access to the Platform, mostly, via a mobile application, and their communication is not only with the Organisation, but also with other users of the same team or coordinators of the same case. Each such user group has a “team leader” who is responsible for the final decision making.

#	EPIC	USER STORY		
		ROLE	GOAL/DESIRE I want...	BENEFIT , so that...
RT.0 1	Profile Editing	S&R Team Member	to be able to edit my personal profile information and add more details regarding my skills, personality or general background.	I can have a more complete personal profile.
RT.0 2	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R Team Member	to get rapidly notified when there is a missing child case and my team is required	I can act on it, get the team assembled and help the investigation in the field.
RT.0 3	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R Team Member	to have access to a discussion channel with my team-members and case coordinators	I can get communicate with my team in a secure and private virtual space and exchange real-time messages
RT.0 4	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R Team Member	to be able to upload/download files of information in the discussion channel	I can exchange multimedia files, like photos or videos, with team-members and my superiors.
RT.0 5	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R Team Member	to get guidance and real-time profiling information about the case from coordinators	I can be constantly informed about the case’s status and act in a more efficient way
RT.0 6	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	S&R Team Member	to be able to watch my current location, as well as other team members’ locations, on an interactive map	I can have a clear overview of the team’s current situation and the area each member covers

III.4 User Stories for Actor “Volunteer Team member”

This actor’s members are considered to be registered and authenticated, logged on users that have access to the Platform, mostly, via a mobile application, and their communication is not only with the Organisation they belong to, but also with other users of the same team or coordinators of the same case. Each such user group has a “team leader” who is responsible for the final decision making.

#	EPIC	USER STORY		
		ROLE	GOAL/DESIRE I want...	BENEFIT , so that...
VT.01	Profile Editing	Volunteer Team Member	to be able to edit my personal profile information and add more details regarding my skills, personality or general background.	I can have a more complete personal profile.
VT.02	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Volunteer Team Member	to get rapidly notified when there is a missing child case and my team is required	I can act on it and help the investigation in the field.
VT.03	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Volunteer Team Member	to have access to a discussion channel with my team-members and case coordinators	I can guide my team in a secure and private virtual space and exchange real-time messages
VT.04	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Volunteer Team Member	to be able to upload/download files of information in the discussion channel	I can exchange multimedia files, like photos or videos, with my team-members and my superiors.
VT.05	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Volunteer Team member	to get guidance and real-time profiling information about the case from coordinators	I can be constantly informed about the case’s status and act in a more efficient way
VT.06	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Volunteer Team Member	to be able to watch my current location, as well as other team members’ locations, on an interactive map	I can have a clear overview of the team’s current situation and the area each member covers

III.5 User Stories for Actor “Hosting Facility Manager”

This user is a registered and authenticated, logged on user that have access to the Platform, mostly, via a web interface. As a person in charge of a hosting facility, this user communicates with the Organisation headquarters, as well as the heads of other facilities and the authorities.

#	EPIC	ROLE	GOAL/DESIRE I want...	BENEFIT , so that...
FM.01	Profile Editing	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to edit my personal profile information and add more details regarding my skills, personality or general background.	I can have a more complete personal profile.
FM.02	Investigation Profiling	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to fill in extended profiling information about an unaccompanied migrant minor residing in the premises	I can keep track of the minors I am responsible for
FM.03	Investigation Profiling	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to find a minor that is documented in the system using multiple profiling criteria and fuzzy matching	when a minor comes to my care, I can have access to his history and be able to notify other facilities that the minor isn't missing
FM.04	Investigation Profiling	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to upload documents to the platform concerning the children of my facility	there is a repository of profile records with the corresponding digital files (e.g. id papers, forms, etc).
FM.05	Investigation Profiling	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to edit/replace the documents I have uploaded to the platform	there is always the updated version of all pieces of information regarding a profile record.
FM.06	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to rapidly notify the Organisation when there is a case of a missing child in my facility	they can act on it and follow the appropriate procedures.
FM.07	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Hosting Facility Manager	the system to automatically notify the managers of other facilities where the child has been before or has friends/relatives there	more people get notified that are relevant to the case.
FM.08	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Hosting Facility Manager	to have access to a collaboration space with teams and case coordinators with the ability to upload/download files	I can offer the necessary information (e.g. a profile record) to the investigation group or my superiors.
FM.09	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Hosting Facility Manager	to be able to ask other facility managers for their input in case they have historical data concerning the same child	I can exchange information with other facilities.

#	EPIC	ROLE	GOAL/DESIRE I want...	USER STORY BENEFIT , so that...
FM.10	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Hosting Facility Manager	to get guidance and real-time information about the case from coordinators	I can be constantly informed about the case's status and act in a more efficient way.

III.6 User Stories for Actor “Organisation Case Manager”

This actor is considered to be a registered and authenticated, logged on user that have access to the Platform, mostly, via a web interface, and his or her communication is not only with the rest of the Organisation roles, but also with the teams assigned to the same case. This user is responsible, information-wise, for a specific case and therefore, will play the role of the initial information feeder.

#	EPIC	USER STORY		
		ROLE	GOAL/DESIRE I want...	BENEFIT , so that...
CM.01	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to fill in the basic information about a new missing child case	I can provide basic details on that case.
CM.02	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to update the information of a case with more details or specify crucial information (like location last seen, latest info gathered, etc.)	I can offer an updated description of a case.
CM.03	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to upload relevant multimedia files (e.g. pic of child)	I can offer a more informed description of a case.
CM.04	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to add social media accounts of the child	I can enhance the profiling process by using knowledge extraction on social profile preferences, activities, public posts, etc.
CM.05	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to add psychological reviews, witness reports, etc	I can enhance the profiling details of the missing child.
CM.06	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Case Manager	to close and archive a finished case	All people involved get notified and the case is no longer displayed as active.
CM.07	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to engage in real time discussions with user groups (e.g. volunteers, rescue teams)	I can carry forward relevant information in a secure and private virtual space and exchange real-time messages.
CM.08	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to upload/download files of information in the discussion channel	I can exchange multimedia files, like photos or videos, with the case members.
CM.09	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to communicate with the Network Manager	I can pass location-based information to the investigation procedure on the field.

CM.10	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to contact and get guidance by the Organisation Coordinator	I can act in a more efficient way regarding the available resources.
CM.11	Investigation Crowd Sourcing Action	Organisation Case Manager	to initiate a crowd-sourcing evidence validation process	I can receive feedback on the validity of a piece of information.
CM.12	Investigation Crowd Sourcing Action	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to configure the settings of the validation process	I can focus the process to a specific centre and range.
CM.13	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to issue global news and announcements about a case	I can notify all users of important news
CM.14	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to issue directions and information to group of users based on their location	I can notify only users that are actually near a point of interest
CM.15	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to get real-time feedback from all available human resources (e.g. citizens, anonymous users)	I can gather all possible information
CM.16	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to be able through the platform to monitor missing children's social accounts for new public posts	I may extract information on their whereabouts.
CM.17	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to monitor the overall progress of the investigation	I can understand at which state it is
CM.18	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to view all information about a case, sent by all participants, in historical order	I can have a more detailed view on the progress of the investigation
CM.19	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to evaluate the information gathered	I can distribute the important pieces to the relevant teams
CM.20	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Case Manager	to be able to send my evaluation and current status to the Coordinator	the important information propagates to the top.

III.7 User Stories for Actor “Organisation Network Manager”

This actor is considered to be a registered and authenticated, logged on user that have access to the Platform, mostly, via a web interface, and his or her communication is not only with the rest of the Organisation roles, but also with the teams assigned to the same case. This user is responsible, communication-wise, for a specific case and therefore, will play the role of the networking and communication manager.

#	EPIC	ROLE	GOAL/DESIRE I want...	BENEFIT , so that...
NM.01	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	To get notified as soon as there is a new case that requires my skills	I can act rapidly to assemble the appropriate teams
NM.02	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to notify all Search and Rescue Teams or/and Volunteer Teams to log in to the platform	we can setup a collaboration space about the case and the investigation.
NM.03	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to have access or be able to create a discussion channel with the team-members and case coordinators	I can guide my teams in a secure and private virtual space and exchange real-time messages
NM.04	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to communicate with the Case Manager in real-time	I can get the required information for the case.
NM.05	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to contact and get guidance by the Organisation Coordinator	I can be constantly informed about all cases' status and distribute human resources accordingly and more efficiently
NM.06	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to view where all field resources (humans, vehicles, dogs) are located in real-time	I can be constantly informed about the status and whereabouts of all field resources
NM.07	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Network Manager	to monitor the current progress of the investigation location-wise	I can direct teams to search in specific areas
NM.08	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Network Manager	to view predictions regarding the possible routes of the missing child	I can direct teams to search in specific areas

NM.09	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Network Manager	to be able to send my evaluation and current status to the Coordinator	the important information propagates to the top.
--------------	--------------------------	------------------------------	--	--

III.8 User Stories for Actor “Organisation Coordinator”

This actor is considered to be a registered and authenticated, logged on user that have access to the Platform, mostly, via a web interface. This user has the responsibility and coordination for all cases and can communicate vertically with all teams and roles of an Organisation.

#	EPIC	USER STORY		
		ROLE	GOAL/DESIRE I want...	BENEFIT , so that...
OC.1	Investigation Profiling	Organisation Coordinator	To have access to all cases' information and be able to edit, open or close a case	I have total control of all cases.
OC.2	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to contact all Case and Network Managers	I can coordinate all available resources.
OC.3	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to engage in real time discussions with user groups (e.g. volunteers, rescue teams)	I can get real-time feedback from a group of people.
OC.4	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Coordinator	to issue global news and announcements about any case	I can notify all users of important news.
OC.5	Investigation Coordination/ Communication	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to contact each and every user of the platform personally	I can send and get personalised feedback.
OC.6	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Coordinator	to monitor the overall progress of all the active investigations	I can understand at which state is each case and what assistance requires.
OC.7	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Coordinator	to monitor the progress of all active investigations location-wise	I can guide the Network Manager accordingly .
OC.8	Investigation Monitoring	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to view all cases current and past and their full details	I have access to all available information.

OC.9	Investigation Management	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to assign Case and Network Managers for each case	each case is covered in the most efficient way.
OC.10	Investigation Management	Organisation Coordinator	to be able to file a report regarding the management of each case	there is a complete archive for each investigation, not only regarding the goal, but also about the procedures followed by all participants.

III.9 User Stories for Actor “Organisation Owner”

This actor represents an Organisation and is a registered and authenticated, logged on user that have access to the Platform, mostly, via a web interface. This user has the responsibility and coordination for the human resources and the organisation chart of an Organisation.

#	EPIC	USER STORY		
		ROLE	GOAL/DESIRE I want...	BENEFIT , so that...
00.1	Organisation Information Filling	Organisation Owner	to be able to set and edit the basic information about my Organisation	I can provide an informative profile of the Organisation.
00.2	Organisation Management	Organisation Owner	to be able to view a list of all available users belonging to my Organisation and at what position	I can have an overview of our human resources assignments
00.3	Organisation Management	Organisation Owner	to be able to send invitations via e-mail to my personnel and associated teams to join the platform	I can invite them to join the platform and gather all my human resources in this collaboration platform.
00.4	Organisation Management	Organisation Owner	to setup and assign roles for the Organisation members (Case Manager, Network Manager, Coordinator, Volunteer Team member, Search & Rescue Team member)	I can manage the access privileges of my users to the available information and functionality.
00.5	Organisation Management	Organisation Owner	to remove users from my Organisation	I can reorganise our human resources
00.6	Organisation Management	Organisation Owner	to delete my Organisation	it is no longer part of the ChildRescue platform
00.7	Organisation Monitoring	Organisation Owner	to have an overview of all active cases and the human resources (e.g. Organisation members, Volunteers, etc) assigned on each one	I can have a clear picture of the current effort and possible deficiencies
00.8	Organisation Monitoring	Organisation Owner	to have an overview of the duration of all historical cases and the human resources assigned on each one	I can have a clear picture of the past performance of my staff
00.9	Organisation Communication	Organisation Owner	to accept and reply to messages directed to my Organisation by simple users or visitors of the platform	I can respond to user requests/complaints towards the Organisation
00.10	Organisation Communication	Organisation Owner	to be able to communicate with other Organisations	we can cooperate together in a mission or cause

